

OS Awards

European Public Recognition Scheme for Open Source SW/HW Initiatives

D3.1: Cartography of areas in Open Source critical to recognise

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable report explores the role of Open Source Software (OSS) and Open Source Hardware (OSH) as strategic enablers of Europe's digital sovereignty, innovation capacity, and industrial resilience. Conducted under the OSAwards.eu initiative, the study combines desk research, community survey, and expert interviews to identify key technological, governance, and cultural factors shaping openness in Europe. The findings reveal both momentum and fragmentation signalling a need investments into growing skills and capabilities through improved access to open tools and infrastructure, continued investments into open standards, increased funding for academic programs and technology transfer, as well as for long-term maintenance and promotion of industry collaboration. The report highlights the need for increased investments and public recognition across use cases and verticals, as well as legal, business, policy, development, and governance aspects to embed openness as a core value and practical instrument of European technological autonomy.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASIC	Application-Specific Integrated Circuit
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CAM	Computer-Aided Manufacturing
CISC	Complex Instruction Set Computing
CNC	Computer Numerical Control
EC	European Commission
EDA	Electronic Design and Automation
EU	European Union
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Arrays
IC	Integrated circuits
IoT	Internet-of-Things
IPCEI	Important Project for Common European Interest
IPCEI-CIS	Important Project for Common European Interest on Next Generation Cloud Infrastructure and Services
ISA	Instruction Set Architecture
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
OSH	Open Source Hardware
OSPO	Open Source Program Office
OSS	Open Source Software
PC	Project Coordinator
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
PDK	Process Development Kit
PO	Project Office
RISC	Reduced Instruction Set Computing
SBOM	Software Bill of Materials
SoC	System-on-Chip
TF	Task Force
TI	Thematic Initiatives
TM	Technical Manager
TTO	Technology Transfer Office
MS	Member State
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

This report provides a comprehensive analysis of the role of Open Source Software (OSS) and Open Source Hardware (OSH) in advancing Europe’s digital sovereignty, innovation capacity, and industrial resilience. Conducted within the OS Awards.eu Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Action, the study identifies key technological, governance, and policy enablers that position openness as both a strategic asset and a foundational principle of European digital infrastructure. Drawing from extensive desk research, interviews, and survey data, the findings reveal a rapidly evolving but uneven landscape: while open technologies are increasingly embedded in European frameworks such as the European Chips Act, AI Continent Action Plan, and IPCEI-CIS, structural barriers still limit their full potential. These include fragmented governance and stewardship, unequal institutional engagement, dependency on proprietary tools, and a lack of long-term sustainable funding and skills development mechanisms.

The analysis underscores the distinct but interconnected trajectories of OSS and OSH. OSS has become a cornerstone of European digital infrastructure—powering sectors from energy and telecommunications to AI, healthcare, and manufacturing—yet its legal and institutional frameworks remain challenged by compliance burdens, sustainability deficits, and uneven recognition of community contributions. Hardware openness, by contrast, faces higher material, legal, and financial barriers, with design tools, certification systems, and manufacturing infrastructure often controlled by non-European entities. Nevertheless, promising cases such as OpenFlexure, Open Source Imaging Initiative, lowRISC, and the OpenHW Foundation show that stewardship, transparent governance, and public investment can scale openness into sustainable ecosystems.

OSS and OSH need for considering both in conjunction. On the one hand, software essentially comprises of ones and zeros, while hardware comprises of atoms. On the other, physical hardware today is a result of a digital fabrication process. This means that there is a strong reliance on software also in the hardware context, which is also the platform on which software runs.

The report calls for coordinated policy action to strengthen Europe’s capacity to develop, govern, and maintain open ecosystems across all sectors. It recommends investments in open tooling, design and fabrication infrastructure, workforce training, increased funding to academic programs, investments into strategic open standards, and long-term maintenance funding, combined with governance reform through technology transfer mechanisms between industry and academia. Public recognition mechanisms—such as the European Open Source Awards and Academy—provide catalysts for cultivating a European culture of openness, transparency, and collaboration. Building on the report’s findings, the recognition frameworks should celebrate those advancing shared governance, transparent tooling, reproducible science, or open industrial design—making openness itself a recognised dimension of European excellence. In doing so, Europe can anchor openness not merely as a compliance principle, but as a strategic and cultural asset for innovation, resilience, and societal progress.

1 Introduction

Open Source Software (OSS) and Open Source Hardware (OSH) make up critical levers for enabling Europe's digital future, competitiveness, and strategic autonomy. Yet, awareness, knowledge, and culture are lacking across many parts of society. There is a need to increasing Europe's skills and capabilities related to OSS and OSH for the continent's industry to keep pace with global competition. As geopolitics keep on influencing relationships and supply-chains, there is further need for Europe to increase its influence and control of its digital infrastructure and wider sphere of interest.

To support Europe's growth of skills and capabilities to leverage OSS and OSH accordingly, the OS Awards.eu project, a Horizon-funded Coordination and Support Action, is establishing a system of European annual awards that can act as a lighthouse to encourage increased contribution to, integration of, and exploitation of open source assets.

This report presents a deliverable in the context of this work, aiming to identify the relevant areas to recognize that will be the baseline for the categories to be considered in the awards. The report identifies enablers, challenges, and barriers for Open Source recognition to enrich the characterization of the dimensions in the awards and derive proper policy related recommendations towards the sustainability of the public recognition framework. Specifically, we asked the question:

- RQ: What areas of technology, society and industry in the context of OSS and OSH respectively are critical in the context of Europe's competitiveness and open strategic autonomy?

A qualitative research approach was adopted through a combination of desk research, a community survey, and semi-structured interviews with domain experts, The findings provide an empirical foundation for shaping recognition categories and informing policy recommendations within the OS Awards.eu initiative.

The report is structured as follows. First, we present our methodological approach towards conducting the study. Second, we present our synthesized mapping and characterization on the use and adoption of OSH across Europe, focused on a subset of OSH use cases. Third, we present similar investigation focused on the use and adoption of OSS across a number of areas and verticals. Fourth, we perform a cross-case analysis of the OSH use case from legal, business, policy, development and governance perspectives and provide recommendations for public policy and recognition frameworks to consider in terms of investment and recognition efforts. Fifth, similar exercise is performed for OSS across the various areas and verticals. Finally, we present the main conclusions of the study.

2 Methodology

A qualitative research approach was adopted, comprising of 1) a mapping and desk research of literature, 2) community survey, and 3) semi-structured interviews. The first two steps helped narrow down critical areas to consider in both OSS and OSH, as both fields are too wide to cover in completeness. A simplification and prioritization were therefore required. For each area identified, several semi-structured interviews were conducted to gain in-depth and practitioner-oriented understanding of each area. Below, we detail each of the research steps in more detail.

2.1 Desk research and survey

In the first step, we aimed to create an initial landscape overview of critical areas to recognize. This was achieved through two streams of work conducted in parallel. First, through desk research of literature (academic, grey, white) available via online sources¹. Second, through a lightweight survey² collecting initial insights from the community to further help guide the mapping process. The questionnaire (see Annex A) was based on the RQs as defined above and refined further simplify understanding by external respondents. The questionnaire was distributed via the EC Survey tool via several communication channels of the OS Awards.eu consortium, including the OpenForum Europe, EC OSPO network, and NexusForum community mailing lists.

The data was collected and compiled in a joint spreadsheet between the involved research partners and discussed on a regular bi-weekly cadence. Thematic analysis³ was used to continuously synthesise responses into higher level themes of relevant areas to consider in continued research process. The landscape overview was discussed with four OSS and OSH experts from the European Open Source Academy to validate and revise based on their in-depth knowledge and experience. Based on the synthesised data, a set of areas were identified as candidates for continued investigation (see table 1).

Table 1: Overview of potential areas for continued investigation of the research process.

Areas of technology	Parts of digital infrastructure	Industries and public infrastructure
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¹ Garousi, V., Felderer, M., Mäntylä, M. V., & Rainer, A. (2020). Benefitting from the grey literature in software engineering research. In *Contemporary Empirical Methods in Software Engineering* (pp. 385-413). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

² Linaker, J., Sulaman, S. M., Höst, M., & de Mello, R. M. (2015). Guidelines for conducting surveys in software engineering v. 1.1. *Lund University*, 50, 1-64.

³ Cruzes, D. S., & Dyba, T. (2011, September). Recommended steps for thematic synthesis in software engineering. In *2011 international symposium on empirical software engineering and measurement* (pp. 275-284). IEEE.

Cloud-Edge-Computing & IoT Artificial Intelligence Cyber Security	Programming language and tooling Network and data transfer Databases and file management Virtualization and containerization Web (front and backend) Desktop suites and applications (incl. Communication and collaboration) Software defined hardware Open compute infrastructure Hardware security	Smart Cities Transportation Education Telecommunications Manufacturing Energy/Utilities Healthcare Automotive Agriculture
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2.2 Semi-structured interviews

To gain further qualitative understanding for each of the areas, semi-structured interviews with experts was adopted as the main approach for data collection in the second step of the research process⁴. Due to the vastness and complexity in scope of the technical category highlighting the various parts of the digital infrastructure (ranging from programming languages and tools to hardware security), this was excluded from the continued data collection.

For the rest of the areas, industry experts were sampled from the networks of the OS Awards.eu consortia partners, with on two or three interviews conducted for each area. Interviews were either conducted online or physically, lasting for about 60 minutes, and recorded for note-taking purposes. The sub-research questions were used as open-ended questions in a semi-structured questionnaire and contextualised for the concerned area based on knowledge acquired from the desk research and community survey in the previous research step. The two authors divided the interviewees equally amongst each other and performed them individually.

Findings were synthesised continuously through thematic analysis using an abductive approach, taking point both from the data, and high-level categories as defined by the sub-research questions. Codes and themes were discussed internally among the two authors to create a common understanding, and needs for potential complementary inputs or clarifications from additional interviews.

⁴ Melegati, J., Conboy, K., & Graziotin, D. (2024). Qualitative Surveys in Software Engineering Research: Definition, Critical Review, and Guidelines. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*.

Based on the initial interviews, OSH was severely under-represented in the sampling which as mainly focused on industry incumbents recognised as users of OSS. A second round of interviews was therefore conducted using a snowball sampling approach starting from OSH experts present in the European Open Source Academy. Interviews followed the same approach to data collection and synthesis as previous round of interviews. Through the iterative synthesis, five high-level areas were conceptualised in the context of OSH, while the more industry- vertical structure was kept for OSS. Areas finally included are presented in table 2 and further presented in detail in the following sections of this report.

Table 2: Overview of areas synthesised through interviews and thematic analysis.

Areas of technology in OSH	Industries and public infrastructure in OSS	Areas of technology in OSS
Open Source Silicon	Energy	Cloud-Edge-Computing
Open Source Data Center & Networking Hardware	Healthcare	Artificial Intelligence
Open Source Electronics	Smart Cities	Cyber Security
Open Source Mechanical Hardware	Transportation	
Open Source Scientific Hardware	Telecommunications	
	Manufacturing	
	Automotive	
	Agriculture	

In total, 37 interviews were conducted with industry experts listed in table 3 in Annex B. All interviewees were presented with the manuscript and offered opportunity to revise and correct any statements and descriptions related to the respective areas.

3 Areas in Open Source Hardware critical to recognise

Open Source Hardware (OSH) can be defined, per the Open Source Hardware Alliance (OSHW), as hardware whose design is made publicly available so that anyone can study, modify, distribute, make, and sell the design or hardware based on that design. The source, including design specifications, software and documentation should be released in a form that can be easily modified. OSH should further use components, processes, infrastructure, and tools that promote (rather than limit) sharing and reuse of the open technology. As with OSS, no use cases or users should be discriminated against, and commercial adoption is supported.

Below, we synthesise and characterise several subfields of OSH, including Open Source Silicon, Data Centre & Networking Hardware, Electronics, Mechanical Hardware, and Scientific Hardware. We recognise that this is a simplification as OSH in nature is too deep and wide to rightfully capture and describe in any overview. Still, it provides a foundational understanding and insights into some of the main areas of OSH of specific importance and value for Europe.

3.1 Open Source Silicon

Open Source Silicon⁵ refers to silicon chips (such as processor cores, accelerators, IP blocks, and system-on-chip components) whose design is open in its entirety, from the high-level hardware description, all the way down to the layout (in line with the OSH definition). The silicon chips are designed, simulated and tested using EDA tools (Electronic Design Automation tools), which are specialised software suites that automate the complex process of designing electronic systems, particularly integrated circuits (ICs), printed circuit boards (PCBs), and system-on-chips (SoCs). Designs are typically described through a hardware description language such as Verilog or VHDL. A Process Development Kit (PDK) is then used to tailor the silicon chip design to the foundry that is to manufacture the chips. The PDK will be specific for each foundry.

3.1.1 A critical component for Europe's strategic autonomy

Silicon chips constitute a critical component used in nearly every modern technology and industry, from automotive, cloud, Internet of Things, connectivity, space, defence and supercomputers⁶. Europe dependence on a limited few Asian and US foundries has caused worry, as disruptions in the supply-chains can have enormous consequences. The risks attached was realised during the Covid-19 pandemic where, e.g., European automotive manufacturers were forced to stop production due to global supply chain disruptions of silicon chips.

⁵ https://wiki.f-si.org/images/1/19/Recommendations_and_roadmap_open_silicon_2023_11_03.pdf

⁶ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-chips-act_en

In a strive to increase the strategic autonomy of Europe, the EU recently introduced the European Chips Act⁷ (Regulation (EU) 2023/1781), a legislative package to support semiconductor manufacturing and innovation until at least 2030. Objectives include increasing Europe's share of the global semiconductor market from less than 10% to 20% by 2030, and strengthening Europe's technological leadership in semiconductor research, design, manufacturing, and packaging. Several challenges need special attention for such vision to realise.

3.1.2 Fabrication capabilities focused on commodity technology

The largest foundries of advanced commercial grade chip manufacturing include TSMC (Taiwan), Samsung Foundry (South Korea), GlobalFoundries (mainly US), SMIC (China), and UMC (Taiwan) share 90%+ of the global market in terms⁸ (with TSMC making up about 60% of total share). Gaining access to these foundries is characterised as expensive and complex, taking up to two years, and effectively blocking many SMEs and new entrants to markets requiring the latest technology chip sets. What foundry to use needs to be identified in the initial phases of any design process, as it will impact the overall design, and implicitly which Process Development Kit (PDK) is to be used to tailor the silicon chip design to the foundry's specific requirements.

Picking up pace and expanding (or creating rather) a European share would be considerably difficult and expensive per the interviewees. Focus is instead encouraged to shift to enable and improve manufacturing of special and legacy-node chips and become as self-sufficient as possible (90%+) in regard to European industry's needs, which typically includes automotive and industrial applications⁹. X-Fab (Germany), STMicroelectronics (Switzerland/France), and Infineon (Germany) are three prominent examples of European chips manufacturers. One interviewee note that Intel is to establish a foundry in Germany, while still fully owned by the US-based company, and by extension not providing a resolution of the risks related to digital sovereignty.

3.1.3 Proprietary design tools adding barriers to entry

Today, three main commercial EDA tool suites for designing integrated circuits, printed circuit boards, and system-on-chips. These tools are described as having significant cost barriers preventing adoption for SMEs and Academia, limiting the opportunities for promoting growth, innovation and skills development in the context of open source silicon. The commercial options are considered critical for any design of silicon chips aimed for compute or network infrastructure, why many companies rely on their access to the tools accordingly.

Among the three vendors (Synopsis, Cadence, and Siemens), two are non-European (the two former) why digital sovereignty and potential threat of political pressure on the provisioning of these tools is a key concern per several interviewees. One interviewee state that export of the EDA tools from Cadence and Synopsis has already been cut off to China demonstrating the size of

⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/european-chips-act>

⁸ <https://www.counterpointresearch.com/en/insights/global-semiconductor-foundry-market-share>

⁹ <https://www.eusemiconductors.eu/esia>

the risk. Another interviewee considers the situation as less of a risk from a European perspective with Siemens being one of the three.

The OSS EDA tools that do exist provide some to adequate support for the design of special and legacy-node chips, but are still in need of substantial investments (“thousands of person years of effort” as expressed by one interviewee) to catch up and keep pace with the commercial technology. Yet, they offer a potential solution for addressing Europe’s technological debt and an opportunity to grow capabilities and self-sufficiency in the commodity spectra of chip design. Stakeholders such as the FOSSi Foundation¹⁰ argue for the crucial role OSS EDA tools play in supporting the ambitious objectives of the European Chips Act. By enhancing accessibility and fostering the development of expertise, they also contribute to strengthening technological sovereignty.

Interviewees further raise the point that the commercial tool vendors have started to show interest in the OSS options as it provides an opportunity for growing skills and adoption, and market expansion also for their commercial tools offerings. One interviewee exemplifies how the US-based DARPA (Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency) several years ago sponsored the development of an OSS-based fully automated EDA tool chain. While the funded projects failed with the ambitious goal, many of the outputs provided foundation and inputs for the OSS EDA tools actively developed today.

3.1.4 Skills gap in chip design and fabrication

Skilled engineers in the context of hardware design is a scarcity for Europe, a challenge raised by several interviewees. There is quality but not the quantity. A recent survey points out Process Engineers and Technicians, IC Design Engineers, and EDA tool developers as roles where there is currently an acute shortage¹¹. Another report¹² suggests a potential talent gap of engineers beyond 100,000 in Europe, citing a generational shift with highly talented senior engineers passing into retirement, limited interest in relevant higher education, and shifting talent needs, e.g., related to AI and machine learning.

Research labs as ones in ETH Zürich, University of Bologna, TU Delft and University of Sheffield are praised by interviewees for producing quality higher-education programmes and students due to their applied research in the field, yet more are needed. Directed funding for research and for higher-education programmes are prompted for as exemplified through the Edu4Chip project, a hands-on master’s course program in Advanced Chip Design, offered by a consortium of five European universities.

¹⁰ <https://fossi-foundation.org/resources/eu-roadmap>

¹¹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/semiconductor-sector-study/semiconductor-sector-study>

¹² <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/semiconductors/our-insights/how-semiconductor-companies-can-fill-the-expanding-talent-gap>

OSS tools (e.g., EDA tools) are further highlighted as a means for enabling improved and increased availability of training and education opportunities, as these can help to lower the barriers to entry for teachers and students. Documentation and training material related to the tooling is highlighted as specifically important.

3.1.5 European and national funding – an enabler for open source silicon

In line with the European Chips act, several funding initiatives are running to boost the European R&I initiatives and capabilities related to silicon chips research and manufacturing. One notable example is EuroHPC, formally known as the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU), which is a major European public-private partnership established in 2018. The Chips Joint Undertaking (Chips JU) is another major European partnership established in 2023 designed to boost the development, innovation, and manufacturing capacities for semiconductor technologies within Europe. Chips JU directly funds projects aimed at developing and disseminating OSS EDA tools.

National funding is also increasing. Germany's "Design Instruments for Sovereign Chip Development with Open Source (DE:Sign)" program one example, which supports R&D, EDA tools, and open IP libraries. The legislative package attached to the Chips Act further also include non-competitive state funding

3.1.6 Research and Innovation growing capabilities in chip design

There are several R&I projects and initiatives working towards growing Europe's capabilities and strategic autonomy where open source silicon is a key tool and enabler. The Chips Act, e.g., comes with the Chips for Europe initiative (operated under the Chips JU), which is focused on setting up an open-access, cloud-based virtual environment for chip design, supporting the development of and integrating said OSS EDA tools, as well as IP libraries, and support services, allowing researchers and developers to experiment with new architectures more freely and affordably.

In addition, multiple projects receiving funding from, e.g., EuroHPC, Chips JU, and Horizon programs, in several ways synergise and overlap in building on and contributing to RISC-V, an open standard Instruction Set Architecture (ISA). The standard provides formal specification when designing silicon chips that defines how software communicates with hardware interface.

3.2 Open Source Data Center & Networking Hardware

OSH in the context of data centre and networking hardware regards open designs and specifications of the physical devices and equipment that store, process, and move large volumes of data between computers, servers, and users. This includes servers (for computing), storage systems (for saving data), and networking equipment like switches and routers (for connecting everything together), as well as essential supporting infrastructure such as power supplies and cooling systems that enable the operations. A foundational building block also covered is the microprocessor, a subset of the silicon chips that performs the complex compute operations inside the servers.

3.2.1 Strategic importance of the microprocessors to data centre stack

Access to advanced computing hardware is increasingly shaped by geopolitical dynamics. One interviewee illustrates the point through China's attempts to circumvent export restrictions on AI accelerators. Proprietary architectures such as x86, controlled by a limited number of vendors, pose significant risks for countries and organisations seeking technological independence as political pressure from the home countries can seriously impact supply to, for example, Europe. These dependencies can further hinder critical sectors if updates or support are withdrawn. As a vast majority of cloud services are procured from non-European vendors¹³, acquiring European cloud and compute capabilities is critical to be able to store and process data in safe environments per EU data legislation and requirements.

Maintaining access to the latest microprocessor technology becomes ever more critical for Europe in its attempt to increase pace in developing compute capabilities for AI. The recent AI Continent Action Plan¹⁴ highlights EU's aim to make Europe a global leader in AI, announcing investments into a network of 13 AI Factories at existing supercomputers across Europe. These are to support and enable development and research into AI models and applications by European AI startups, industry and researchers. An additional number of "AI Gigafactories" is also announced, funded through public-private partnerships. Each Gigafactory is expected to have a capacity corresponding to four single AI factories. Additional stimulus is expected through the announced (yet to be implemented) Cloud and AI Development Act where an underpinning goal is to at least triple the EU's data centre capacity in the next five to seven years.

3.2.2 Strategic investments into open standards critical to maintain openness

While OSH offers clear benefits for education and capacity building, its broader role as a driver of industrial competitiveness remains constrained. The hardware domain is deeply shaped by proprietary tooling, patent entanglements, and high development costs, which limit the feasibility of open innovation. A notable example is the dominance of Nvidia in AI hardware, where

¹³ <https://www.datacenterdynamics.com/en/news/european-cloud-providers-hold-15-of-local-market-share-synergy-research/>

¹⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_25_1013

proprietary software frameworks such as CUDA have become tightly coupled with GPU architectures. This coupling creates significant barriers to portability and reuse, as AI models are often optimized for specific vendor platforms. In contrast, open standards—such as those emerging around RISC-V—offer a potential path toward more flexible and sovereign alternatives.

Open standards, such as RISC-V, should accordingly be prioritized through investments, influence and adoption. They provide a shared technical foundation that enables interoperability across institutions, regions, and projects. To maximize their impact, specific categories of standards should be prioritized. Instruction set architectures (ISAs), such as RISC-V, are foundational for enabling open and extensible processor design. Interconnect standards are also critical, as they determine how components communicate within a system and influence modularity and reuse. Process design standards, including those related to fabrication and packaging, are necessary to ensure compatibility and reproducibility across different manufacturing environments.

3.2.3 Open Instruction Set Architectures and RISC-V

Historically, processor architectures have been divided into RISC (Reduced Instruction Set Computing) and CISC (Complex Instruction Set Computing). While CISC architectures like x86 have dominated high-performance computing, RISC architectures have gained traction in mobile and embedded systems. The shift initiated by companies like Apple, which transitioned from Intel to ARM-based designs, illustrates (per interviewees) the growing viability of RISC architectures in mainstream computing.

RISC-V has emerged as the leading open instruction set architecture (ISA) for silicon chip design, providing a foundation for custom processors without the constraints of proprietary licensing. Its adoption is growing across sectors, from embedded devices to automotive and even server-grade applications, and it is seen as a strategic opportunity for Europe to reduce dependency on dominant U.S. and Asian chip vendors. RISC-V's open standard enables greater technological sovereignty and flexibility, and it has already lowered barriers for academic and SME participation in chip design, fostering collaborative innovation and shared development costs.

However, the openness of RISC-V does not automatically translate to fully open hardware. Actual chip production still relies on proprietary EDA tools, manufacturing processes, and global supply chains, meaning that RISC-V chips are not “open source hardware” in the complete sense. While the software ecosystem is mature—Linux and other platforms already support RISC-V—the next major challenges are in manufacturing capacity, open tooling, and coordinated investment, especially for high-performance and server-grade chips.

While the software stack around RISC-V is maturing, as signalled through upcoming support in the OSS Operating System Ubuntu, there are severe limitations when considering vertical-specific software implementations. One interviewee describes how the Automotive industry was held back due to lack of support for RISC-V in QNX, a real-time operating system (RTOS) in automotive systems, developed by Blackberry QNX, an American vendor. The interviewee believes this to be a difficult problem to solve because each industry has a number of often proprietary tools that are important specifically to them, but that no one else cares about.

3.2.4 Prioritize investments into skills, open source tools, academic and R&D

However, OSH is considered by scepticism by some interviewees as a means for gaining autonomy, which in one case is described as a “pipe dream” due to lack of culture, funding and commercial traction. Accelerating R&D in Europe to catch up with American and Chinese technology clusters is described as impossible and a potential black hole for funding. Rather it is suggested to leverage OSH as a means for growing skills and technical talent in Europe by enabling accessibility to OSS EDA tools and design infrastructure, while investing in academic programs such as the ones delivered from ETH Zurich.

The academic sphere, including ETH Zurich is further characterized by many as the main source of innovative technology in Europe. The PULP platform from ETH Zurich has generated several derivatives including ones that have been picked up by the UK-based not-for-profit company lowRISC and further developed into commercial grade IP products. Accordingly, investments into technology transfer and research programs promoting industry-academia collaboration are also prompted as key for growing capabilities necessary to improve Europe’s position capabilities.

3.2.5 Standardising server and rack-level infrastructure

Processor development is only one part of the equation; complete systems require compatible boards, memory, and power management. The Open Compute Project (OCP) addresses this by promoting the collaborative development of open and standardized hardware specifications for server and rack-level infrastructure. This includes specifications for power electronics, cooling systems, and secure management interfaces, all of which are critical for high-density data centre environments. Standardisation at this level enables interoperability and simplifies deployment as described by one interviewee representing OCP.

The project has evolved from a U.S.-centric initiative into a global ecosystem, providing open designs and specifications that reduce costs and increase flexibility. Its governance model, like that of the Linux Foundation or RISC-V Foundation, is non-political and community-driven. Europe in a sense has limited influence within OCP as most influence is maintained by non-European tech companies. Yet, the initiative remains a key enabler for open infrastructure development and for Europe’s future strategic autonomy.

By sharing 3D models, bills of materials, and design files, OCP enables organisations to build and customise hardware without vendor lock-in. European projects are increasingly referencing OCP standards, and proof-of-concept systems are being developed that rival commercial offerings from previous years. However, the pace of development is hindered, per one interviewee, by bureaucratic processes and fragmented decision-making. In contrast, companies like Nvidia can rapidly mobilise investment and bring products to market. This disparity highlights the need for more agile and coordinated approaches within the EU.

OCP is not only focused on sharing 3D models, but also try to create a more unified and interoperable ecosystem for data centre hardware. OCP Modular Hardware System¹⁵ (MHS)

¹⁵ <https://www.opencompute.org/projects/mhs>

Subproject provides an example defining standard interfaces and form factors, and thereby allowing components from different manufacturers to work together seamlessly. This reduces vendor lock-in and gives data centre operators more flexibility in their hardware choices, and per interviewees considered important for European efforts of building sovereign hardware.

3.3 Open Source Electronics

Open source electronic covers a higher level of abstraction in relation to open source silicon and microprocessor, considering the design and sharing of complete electronic systems, devices, modules, and boards—primarily at the circuit and PCB (Printed Circuit Board) level, that in turn use the silicon chips as critical components¹⁶. The design files typically include schematics, PCB layouts, Bills of Materials, and sometimes firmware for embedded systems—everything needed to build and reproduce an electronic device (but not the internal silicon design).

3.3.1 Tools and platforms for designing circuit and PCB boards

PCBs are flat boards consisting of insulating material such as fiberglass with conductive copper traces etched onto its surface to form electrical connections between electronic components¹⁷. The term “circuit board” is often used interchangeably with PCB, but technically, “circuit board” is a general term for any board supporting electrical circuits, while “PCB” specifically refers to boards made using printed patterns of copper traces.

There are a few open PCB platforms available. Arduino¹⁸ is the most renowned per interviewees. BeagleBoard¹⁹ is an alternative platform also cited. These boards can be ordered by fabricating companies, such as Arduino, the company behind the product with the same name. Users can still, however, use the designs and OSS tools accompanied with these tools to make their own designs and improvements.

A general and mature design tool iterated by several interviewees includes the KiCAD²⁰ project, Electronic Design Automation (EDA) tools for PCB design (cf. EDA tools for silicon chip design). The tool is heavily used by CERN, which is also a key contributor, e.g., by dedicating their own development resources as well as funding external developers to work on the project.

3.3.2 Support and processes missing for open collaboration

Designs are commonly shared via the communities surrounding the various PCB design tools and hardware platforms, or more general platforms such as OSHWA Labs²¹. Arduino describes how their community interaction—facilitated through a large and active forum—plays a critical role in identifying design flaws, suggesting improvements, and shaping features. The project’s iterative manufacturing approach and small batch production allows for rapid feedback and correction.

¹⁶ <https://arshon.com/blog/the-rise-of-open-source-hardware-in-electronics-design-a-revolution-in-innovation/>

¹⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Printed_circuit_board

¹⁸ <https://www.arduino.cc/>

¹⁹ <https://docs.beagle.cc/>

²⁰ <https://www.kicad.org/>

²¹ <https://oshwlab.com/>

This form of open collaboration is, however, typically limited to knowledge sharing only as both processes and tools are generally missing that allows for a collaborative workflow similar to OSS development, including forking, version control, and pull requests. Although design files are openly shared and hosted on platforms like GitHub, the tooling ecosystem for hardware lacks the seamless integration found in software.

While Arduino maintains open forums and documentation repositories, and encourages community contributions through platforms like Project Hub²², the lack of centralised support for user-generated board designs reflects the complexity of managing physical artifacts. Supporting forks of hardware designs introduces logistical and legal challenges, especially when quality control and customer support are involved.

3.3.3 Certification and component licensing further limiting de-facto openness

While many projects, such as Arduino, make their design files openly available, critics argue that true openness requires access to detailed manufacturing specifications—including, for example, material properties, copper thickness, paint layers, and fabrication processes. These parameters directly affect the ability to certify a board under standards such as CE, FCC, or regional equivalents, which are prerequisites for entering public tenders or commercial markets. Certification is required for industrial or educational deployment of any embedded product leveraging the PCB.

Moreover, certification is factory-specific; a board manufactured in one facility cannot automatically retain its certification if produced elsewhere, even with identical design files. This limits the replicability of certified designs and introduces barriers for third-party manufacturers.

Additional constraints arise from proprietary elements such as USB vendor IDs, which may be required. Vendor IDs are unique for the vendors, allowing product IDs for each USB component to be bought and licensed from a USB Special Interest Group (SIG). If other than the vendor starts using the original vendor ID, the vendor at hand could lose its licence, and ability to procure and implement USB technology in its PCBs. Same issue concerns, e.g., Bluetooth components.

These legal and technical limitations mean that while the design may be open, full replication and deployment often require navigating complex certification regimes and proprietary licensing agreements.

3.3.4 Supply chain dependencies and sovereignty in European hardware manufacturing

While Europe retains some capacity for PCB manufacturing, particularly for low- to mid-complexity designs, sovereignty challenges persist across the broader hardware supply chain. High-layer PCBs—such as 8- or 10-layer boards—are often prototyped domestically but outsourced to China for high-yield production, even by companies with European facilities. This reflects a broader pattern of dependency not only on chip-level components, which are largely sourced from Taiwan

²²<https://projecthub.arduino.cc/>

and the U.S., but also on passive components like resistors and capacitors. These are predominantly manufactured in China, with limited European production capacity.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, Arduino experienced firsthand the fragility of this supply chain, facing significant logistical and cost barriers to sourcing basic components like resistors. The situation underscores that sovereignty concerns extend beyond semiconductors to include the entire stack of electronic components.

Strategic responses may include investing in wafer fabrication near raw material sources—such as the silicon mine in Pontevedra, Spain—and developing domestic capabilities in chip packaging and passive component manufacturing. While chip production garners the most attention, rebuilding foundational manufacturing infrastructure for components often overlooked in policy discussions could be a more attainable and impactful step toward reducing European dependency and enhancing resilience.

3.4 Open Source Mechanical Hardware

Open Source Mechanical Hardware encompasses tools, methods and processes for designing and fabricating physical and mechanical OSH components and products. These physical objects can be powered and given digital capabilities with use of electronic components such as circuit boards and PCBs but is not necessarily the case.

3.4.1 Power and agency enabled through distributed manufacturing

Science is commonly cited example, supporting scientists in building tools and machines tailored to their specific tasks. This often involves small-scale, distributed production, though distributed manufacturing itself is not the goal. The aim is to give researchers agency over their hardware, enabling them to adapt and extend designs as needed. In Europe, mechanical OSH is particularly vibrant, with communities working on open science tools like OpenFlexure²³ and OpenPCR²⁴. Beyond science, there are networks focused on agricultural tools and sustainable design, especially in France and Spain. These projects often intersect with self-sufficiency movements and low-tech philosophies.

Healthcare is another domain where OSH has shown potential, particularly in contexts requiring customisation. Projects like E-Nable's prosthetic hand design and open ventilator initiatives during COVID-19 illustrate how OSH can respond to urgent needs. The pandemic also saw large-scale production of face shields via 3D printing, though their utility was ultimately limited compared to masks. These efforts raised important questions about distributed quality control. While the crisis catalysed collaboration and experimentation, the return of global supply chains has dampened some of that momentum. Still, the experience demonstrated how OSH can mobilise communities and resources in times of need.

In Ukraine, OSH has been used in the context of warfare, with communities sharing designs for drones and other devices. Licensing is often informal, but the collaborative spirit remains strong. Much of the work focuses on calibration and quality assurance, requiring coordination across distributed actors. This illustrates how OSH can be adapted to high-stakes environments, though it also raises ethical and governance questions.

3.4.2 Open source CAD tools catching up but lack collaborative workflow

A central challenge in the design and manufacturing of physical OSH is the reliance on proprietary software. While FreeCAD is not yet as mature as commercial CAD packages, it remains the closest open alternative and holds significant promise for both educational and professional contexts. The tool is used heavily in the Open Source Imaging Initiative (OSI²), where a representative highlights the value of creating interoperable workflows and interfaces to outside tools outside of FreeCAD. OSI², for example, rely on FreeCAD to perform the balance magnets constructed, done with help

²³ <https://openflexure.org/>

²⁴ <https://openpcr.org/>

of an OSH robot that does the measurement, and inputs the data to FreeCAD through a script, that in turn shapes 3D models, which can be produced through an OSH printer - A process described as cumbersome and complex to be copied in a proprietary ecosystem.

One area where FreeCAD is reported to lag behind proprietary options is in terms of usability and simulation capabilities, where the former is common challenge for OSS in general. Simulation capabilities—such as finite element analysis and multi-body simulation—are improving in open tools such as FreeCAD but remain less mature compared to proprietary platforms. Enhanced simulation would allow for greater trust in OSH designs before physical prototyping, mirroring the role of test suites in software development.

Collaboration on physical products is also more challenging than in software, as platforms like GitHub are not optimised for hardware artifacts. One interviewee raises the need for cloud-based collaboration platforms that can integrate tools like FreeCAD and KiCAD, supporting distributed teamwork and more seamless project development. One interviewee highlights, though, that some OSS CAD tools can allow for CAD models to be represented as code, and that there are tool available for GitLab and other platforms that can unpacks FreeCAD files automatically to make them git-compatible. Platforms like WikiFactory²⁵ and Internet of Production²⁶ are working to make hardware designs more searchable and accessible, but binary CAD files and expensive licenses still limit open collaboration.

One interviewee highlights how the broader public would benefit from CAD tools defined by open standards and interoperable file formats, rather than being drawn into proprietary ecosystems through university contracts or industry norms.

3.4.3 Code-native CAD design shows alternative path towards collaboration

An alternative approach is presented by the OpenFlexure project, which draws on software development practices, using code to define the shapes and physical properties of their designs. This software-native design process enables the community to use the same proved infrastructure as OSS projects, such GitHub, providing features such as versioning and collaborative documentation to manage its hardware project. For example, tracking the number of screws needed for assembly is handled much like managing dependencies in software.

Everyone on the core team have enough software background to be comfortable to use this approach, while it provides a barrier to entry for many potential contributors and adopters, looking to customise the product to their specific needs.

3.4.4 Software for fabrication machinery in need of improvement

A related challenge in OSH is the limited availability of OSS for controlling machines. While 3D printing is well supported, areas such as computer-aided manufacturing (CAM) and laser cutting

²⁵<https://wikifactory.com/platform/>

²⁶<https://www.internetofproduction.org/>

still rely on a patchwork of tools—FreeCAD offers a CAM package, and CNC Linux is used for laser cutting, but the ecosystem remains fragmented. In contrast, proprietary CAD suites like Fusion provide integrated solutions with add-ons for every stage of the workflow. However, the OSH community often prefers a modular, “Linux mentality” approach, connecting specialised tools rather than relying on a single, monolithic platform.

3.4.5 Inclusive design promotes impact and adoption

Just as OSS developers need to consider the generalisability of their projects, OSH developers need to consider the needs of their user communities, and no single specific use cases. Involving the users and various stakeholders in the design process, and enabling continuous feedback loops is, hence, essential for enabling any form of broader adoption. So is also the need to consider how the product is to be fabricated and based on what materials. Certain choices may limit implementation, and sustainability of the product. The Open Source Imaging Initiative (OSI²) project has raised these concerns as their goal is to enable widespread adoption in especially the Global South and low-to-middle income countries.

3.4.6 Commercial competition in a global market

In Europe, mechanical OSH has been particularly visible through the 3D printing community, with companies like Ultimaker²⁷ and Prusa²⁸ historically embracing open designs. However, the landscape has shifted. Increasing competition—particularly from Chinese manufacturers—has led many companies to reduce their openness. While these manufacturers often improve scalability and reduce production costs, they also introduce tensions around sustainability and market survival.

There have been calls to boycott certain products, especially in the 3D printing space, but the reality is that manufacturing remains deeply globalised. Much of the innovation in manufacturability and cost-efficiency comes from these actors, even if it complicates the business models of smaller OSH companies.

3.4.7 Open Source Hardware beyond electronics

The open design movement intersects with OSH in various ways, often through ecological or educational initiatives. Projects emerge periodically, accompanied by outreach materials and publications—such as the Dutch book *Open Design Now*. OSH is not limited to electronics; it includes mechanical systems, agricultural tools, and even biomaterials. One interviewee describes the boundaries between hardware and software-defined systems as increasingly blurred and tend to view all shared design outputs as part of the hardware spectrum.

²⁷ <https://ultimaker.com/>

²⁸ <https://www.prusa3d.com/>

Knowledge sharing remains a central motivation. Projects like Public Lab²⁹, which mapped oil spills using balloon-mounted cameras, show how simple technologies can be repurposed for public science. At the other end of the spectrum, large-scale scientific infrastructure—such as gravitational wave detectors—may be open source in principle but are inaccessible in practice due to cost and complexity.

Another example raised by an interviewee regards the Open Footwear project³⁰, an open source shoe project designed for minimal material use and local fabrication—requiring only a CNC machine and, optionally, a 3D scanner. This approach enables anyone with access to a fab lab to produce high-quality, customised footwear, reducing reliance on global supply chains. The project originates at from a team in Brno and has a focus on minimising dependence on Chinese manufacturing, reflect a broader shift from mass production toward more individualised, locally adaptable products.

²⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_Lab

³⁰ <https://www.openfootwear.com/>

3.5 Open Science Hardware

OSH is increasingly recognised as a foundational component of open science, enabling researchers to design, share, and adapt scientific instruments in ways that promote transparency, reproducibility, and cost-efficiency. It gives researchers agency over their hardware, enabling them to adapt and extend designs as needed. Projects such as open microscopes, bioreactors, and environmental sensors illustrate the potential for OSH to reduce costs and expand access, particularly in resource-constrained settings

3.5.1 International and growing community

The open science hardware movement began gaining traction in the mid-2010s, with early efforts focused on DNA patching and enzyme-based industrial processes. The formation of the Gathering for Open Science Hardware (GOSH)³¹ at CERN, the European organisation for Nuclear Research, in 2015 marked a turning point, bringing together a growing community of researchers and practitioners. Subsequent meetings, including Santiago in 2016, helped articulate a roadmap for OSH and emphasised the expansive nature of science as an ecosystem. These gatherings laid the groundwork for a global network committed to making scientific tools more accessible and adaptable.

After temporary breaks during COVID, GOSH is now picking up pace with their yearly gatherings and have recently established the Open Science Hardware Foundation³², which provides fiscal sponsorship to open science hardware initiatives and researchers. The foundation further provides an institutional face for policy engagement and program development, including workshops, awards, and mentorship for transitioning projects beyond the lab.

Science is commonly cited example, supporting scientists in building tools and machines tailored to their specific tasks. This often involves small-scale, distributed production, though distributed manufacturing itself is not the goal. The aim is to give researchers agency over their hardware, enabling them to adapt and extend designs as needed. In Europe, mechanical OSH is particularly vibrant, with communities working on open science tools like OpenFlexure³³ and OpenPCR³⁴.

3.5.2 Broad sectoral adoption and use cases – Example of White Rabbit

Open science hardware has found strong uptake in disciplines such as microscopy, neuroscience, oceanography, and biology, where customisation and cost reduction are critical. Institutions like CERN, TU Delft, and the University of Sussex have emerged as hubs for open research instrumentation. Citizen science initiatives and public-facing research have also benefited from open science hardware, particularly in environmental monitoring and sensing. These applications

³¹ <https://openhardware.science/>

³² <https://opensciencehardware.org/>

³³ <https://openflexure.org/>

³⁴ <https://openpcr.org/>

highlight the versatility of open science hardware and its potential to support both academic and societal goals.

A well-cited example project that has spread beyond the scientific arenas regards the White rabbit project, originating from and hosted by CERN. The project enables time synchronisation across complex infrastructure such as CERN's particle accelerator. Its designs—encompassing hardware, firmware, gateway, and software—are freely accessible, and now used across various places where time synchronisation is critical, such as telecommunications, finance, smart grids, quantum systems, and space technologies.

The project's growth has been enabled by a broad collaboration network comprising research institutions, private companies, and infrastructure operators. A formal White Rabbit Collaboration³⁵ (WRC) was established to coordinate governance, funding, and roadmap priorities across stakeholders³⁶. The WRC functions through a membership model by 2025 including 17 members, where fees sustain maintenance activities managed by a CERN-based bureau. This structure ensures continued stewardship and collaborative development of the open source core, while also enabling new projects to be formed on top. The collaboration's participatory governance model reflects a hybrid public-private partnership, balancing CERN's research mission with industrialization needs and interoperability standards.

3.5.3 Rigorous processes for design, validation and collaboration needed but missing

Open science hardware has special needs and requirements regarding calibration, documentation, and quality control. The lack of standardised tooling and the need for certification—especially in fields like medicine—highlight the importance of robust design practices and institutional support. Trust in instrumentation is often discipline-specific, and journals may require clearer guidelines to evaluate open hardware contributions.

These needs are further challenged by the lack of institutional capacity and support for collaboration in OSH. CERN, recognised by several interviewees as one of the earliest promoters of OSH, highlights a cultural and structural divide between software and hardware communities. While software developers benefited from collaborative platforms and shared learning, hardware designers faced barriers related to tooling, manufacturing, and legal frameworks.

CERN further exemplifies through the White Rabbit project how quality assurance can be ensured through collaborative efforts. The project has dedicated committees development of documentation and training material, as well as for generation of test cases to qualify equipment implementing the White Rabbit technology, which is then certified under the White Rabbit trademark.

³⁵ <https://www.white-rabbit.tech/>

³⁶ Serrano, J. et al. (2024). The White Rabbit Collaboration: An Innovative Model of Public-Private Partnership. <https://epics.anl.gov/icalpecs-2025/pdf/TUPD052.pdf>

3.5.4 Technology transfer offices driven by closed mindsets

One of the persistent challenges in advancing open science hardware within and beyond academic and research institutions is the prevailing orientation of Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) toward proprietary dissemination. Influenced by policy and economic narratives from the 1980s and 1990s, many TTOs operate under the assumption that commercialisation through licensing to private vendors is the most efficient and sustainable pathway for public research outputs. This mindset has become institutionalised, with proprietary licensing often seen as a prerequisite for securing funding and demonstrating impact.

As a result, researchers advocating for open source approaches frequently encounter resistance, needing to justify the viability and legitimacy of openness as a model for innovation and dissemination. The tension is not unique to Europe; it reflects a global issue where institutional structures and incentive systems are misaligned with the collaborative and distributed nature of OSH. Bridging this gap requires not only policy reform but also cultural change within research institutions to recognise OSH as a credible and strategic pathway for public value creation.

Academic Open Source Program Offices (OSPOs)³⁷ has recently emerged, constituting support functions to the Academic and Science oriented institutions in leveraging OSH as a lever for open science principles. TTOs are commonly included as part of these OSPOs to enable support for how OSH principles can be used for technology transfer of research outputs during and between research projects. Trinity College London and LERO, both in Ireland, are two examples of Academic OSPOs in Europe. Mentorship and trainings for researchers to adopt an open and collaborative approach and culture towards research is another important aspect raised by several interviewees - areas that the OSAwards.eu project aims to address.

3.5.5 OpenFlexure – from science project to non-profit steward with vendor ecosystem

OpenFlexure presents a case for when the design, while not perfect, proved highly appropriate for distributed manufacturing. Recognising that patenting or commercialising such a design would be both impractical and uninteresting, the inventors opted for early open release. This decision was validated when students in Africa experimented with mass production, and the project quickly connected with the broader GOSH community.

To provide long-term security and sustainability, a non-profit organisation was established to steward the project, recognising that academic environments are well-suited for invention but less so for ongoing maintenance and support. However, the challenge remains to demonstrate impact and attract philanthropic support, especially when considering deployment in contexts like Kenya or Brazil, where promoting a UK-based charity may not be appropriate.

Still, OpenFlexure has managed to foster a network of companies—now around 10–12—that produce and sell kits, many of which emerged from the GOSH community. The Open Science Shop and other initiatives have facilitated dialogue and knowledge sharing among vendors. In the U.S.,

³⁷ <https://www.linaker.se/blog/public-sector-open-source-program-offices/>

companies like IORodio sell OpenFlexure microscopes, while several European firms do the same, often returning revenues to charity.

3.5.6 Introducing open science requirements in grants and funding calls

A general call for open science principles in funding calls was raised by several interviewees. The European Commission is considered a key stakeholder and driver through the EU Horizon calls and is recognised for having introduced more requirements on OSS and OSH dissemination. The model is further championing and promotion towards both European and national funding calls to further promote both interoperability and the growing of an open strategic autonomy across Europe.

4 Areas in Open Source Software critical to recognise

4.1 Artificial Intelligence

4.1.1 Push for European leadership through strategic investments

The EU is pushing to make Europe a global leader in AI through its recently announced AI Continent Action Plan³⁸, announcing investments into a network of AI Factories and Gigafactories across Europe. These aim to support AI model and application development by European startups, industry, and researchers. Additional stimulus is expected through the announced (yet to be implemented) Cloud and AI Development Act, where an underpinning goal is to at least triple the EU's data centre capacity in the next five to seven years.

The plan also calls for enhancing data accessibility through the creation of Data Labs within AI Factories and a comprehensive Data Union Strategy for 2025 to facilitate large-scale, high-quality data sharing. The plan further looks to accelerate AI adoption beyond the current 13.5% of EU companies through the upcoming Apply AI Strategy, leveraging AI Factories and European Digital Innovation Hubs in this process.

Strengthening the AI talent pipeline is another key pillar, leveraging international recruitment initiatives like the Talent Pool and Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions, alongside educational programs through the AI Skills Academy.

Sovereignty concerns are increasingly shaping these investments. If Europe is to maintain digital sovereignty, it must ensure the ability to develop, deploy, and operate AI technologies independently—even in the event of a digital blackout. This requires reducing dependencies across the stack, from hardware (e.g., GPUs dominated by Nvidia) to cloud infrastructure (currently reliant on hyperscalers). Strategic investment in compute capacity is therefore critical—not to fragment the ecosystem, but to enable autonomy and resilience.

4.1.2 Adoption of Open Source AI components and models increasing

Since the early calls for more OSS tools and libraries in the context of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) specifically³⁹, there has been a tremendous growth of availability and adoption. An Enterprise survey shows of most organisations (58%) use OSS components in at least

³⁸ ³⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_25_1013

³⁹ Sonnenburg, S., Braun, M. L., Ong, C. S., Bengio, S., Bottou, L., Holmes, G., ... & Williamson, R. (2007). The need for open source software in machine learning. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 8(Oct), 2443-2466

half of their AI/ML projects, with a about a third (34%) using OSS in three-quarters or more of their projects⁴⁰.

Adoption is characterised as most significant in the sectors of education, manufacturing, retail, and financial services, while healthcare and IT exhibit lower reliance on OSS. Similar surveys indicate a similar pattern on the importance of OSS tools and libraries in the development, training, and deployment of AI/ML⁴¹, although still with a limited investment compared to other areas of infrastructure and development support⁴².

In Europe specifically, there is a long tradition of developing such OSS tools and libraries, with scikit-learn, a Python library for ML as a prime example. The project came out of a Google Summer of Code project, to later become adopted and hosted by the INRIA, a French national research institute. While the roots are French, the project has today grown to a global community with 2000+ contributors.

Regarding model development, several European companies are emerging. Mistral and Aleph Alpha, a French and German model vendor respectively are both highlighted as prominent players. Hugging Face is also mentioned as a major stakeholder, both as a platform provider and model developer. While founded in France, the company is today technically a US-owned enterprise.

4.1.3 Security and sustainability of Open Source AI projects main challenges

Security stands out as a critical challenge in the surveys, both in the context of AI/ML and OSS in general. Risks include vulnerability exposure through public code, inclusion of malicious code, susceptibility to adversarial attacks, and data poisoning. Addressing these risks requires robust security measures, such as thorough code reviews, regular audits, trusted sources for OSS components, and best practices advocated by the Open Source Security Foundation (OpenSSF).

Sustainability and long-term maintenance of OSS components also present challenges. A case study on scikit-learn demonstrates how France invests public funding in the project as part of its national AI strategy to strengthen digital sovereignty. This funding enabled long-term staffing and technical planning. Still, it is recommended that funding be diversified and balanced with private support and sponsorship to ensure long-term sustainability.

The upcoming AI Act introduces new obligations for general-purpose AI models, including those under OSS licenses, effective from June 2. While exemptions exist, model providers must still offer

⁴⁰ Anaconda. (2024). Open-Source AI in the Enterprise: Insights from a Survey of IT Leaders. Retrieved from <https://www.anaconda.com/blog/anaconda-state-of-enterprise-open-source-ai>.

⁴¹ McKinsey, the Mozilla Foundation, and the Patrick J. McGovern Foundation. (2025). Open source in the age of AI. Retrieved from <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/mckinsey-digital/our-insights/tech-forward/open-source-in-the-age-of-ai>.

⁴² OpenLogic, Open Source Initiative, and the Eclipse Foundation. (2024). 2024 State of Open Source Report. Retrieved from <https://www.openlogic.com/sites/default/files/pdfs/report-ol-state-of-oss-2024.pdf>.

sufficient detail on training data and perform model evaluations, track serious incidents, and implement adequate cybersecurity measures. A draft template for compliance is available and expected to become a standard.

This regulatory shift will test the OSS AI community, which currently lacks sufficient support and guidance. Actors with legal resources will have a competitive advantage, underscoring the need to enable smaller players to comply effectively.

4.1.4 Stewards and foundations as enablers for sustainable collaboration

Stewards and foundations play a key role in enabling the sustainability of the key tools and libraries in the context of AI/ML (as for OSS in general).

- The scikit-learn Consortium hosted within the INRIA Foundation⁴³ exemplifies how private and public funding and sponsorship can be enabled and coordinated to support development within the scikit-learn project. The consortium works closely with Probabl.ai , a private company, in enabling the funding and coordination.
- The PyTorch Foundation⁴⁴ hosts the PyTorch framework and its ecosystem of industry and academic partners. It supports a variety of initiatives, including developer training, regional events, and the development of OSS tools related to the framework. The foundation is hosted under the wider Linux Foundation and is mainly sponsored through the sponsorship and membership fees.
- Linux Foundation AI and Data⁴⁵ is, as the PyTorch Foundation, also part of the larger Linux Foundation, but focused more generally on hosting and enabling collaboration in AI/ML related OSS projects.

These structures are essential to support not only software development but also the broader AI research communities and open data ecosystems that contribute to model training and evaluation.

⁴³ <https://scikit-learn.fondation-inria.fr/home/>

⁴⁴ <https://pytorch.org/foundation>

⁴⁵ <https://lfaidata.foundation/>

4.2 Cloud-Edge-Computing

4.2.1 Investments toward secure, interoperable, and sustainable cloud infrastructures

Cloud computing constitutes a central component of the EU's Digital Decade framework⁴⁶ and European Data Strategy⁴⁷, serving as an instrument to enhance technological capacity, competitiveness, and environmental sustainability. The EC's policy objectives emphasize the establishment of secure, interoperable, and sustainable cloud infrastructures to support both the public and private sectors. By 2030, the EU aims for 75% of European enterprises to use cloud-edge technologies and to deploy 10,000 climate-neutral and secure edge nodes across the region⁴⁸.

These measures are intended to contribute to what the EC defines as a computing continuum, ensuring that data are processed efficiently while adhering to European norms of data protection, energy conservation, and technological autonomy. Initiatives such as the Important Project for Common European Interest on Next Generation Cloud Infrastructure and Services (IPCEI-CIS)⁴⁹ exemplify a top-down approach from the EU where seven to twelve EU member states mobilizes around €2.6 billion—€1.2 billion in public funding, countered by an estimated €1.4 billion in private investment, supporting research, innovation, and deployment of interoperable, open cloud-edge infrastructures that promote secure data exchange, sustainability, and adherence to European values⁵⁰. Two upcoming IPCEIs are planned for addressing AI and Compute Infrastructure, both said to build on IPCEI-CIS which end in 2026.

Another major dimension of EU's strategy concerns data sovereignty, referring to the capacity to manage digital assets under European legal and regulatory frameworks. Current developments indicate an increasing shift toward sovereign cloud adoption, as approximately 84% of European organizations using cloud services report intentions to transition to such models⁵¹. This shift is associated with the EU's broader regulatory orientation, including initiatives aimed at mitigating risks linked to external dependencies, cybersecurity challenges, and supply chain vulnerabilities. Industrial stakeholders such as SAP, Airbus, and BMW have adopted governance mechanisms

⁴⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/europes-digital-decade>

⁴⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-data-strategy_en

⁴⁸ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cloud-computing>

⁴⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/ipcei-next-generation-cloud-infrastructure-and-services-boost-europes-digital-decade>

⁵⁰ https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/state-aid/ipcei/approved-ipceis/cloud_en

⁵¹ <https://www.bearingpoint.com/en/insights-events/insights/data-sovereignty-the-driving-force-behind-europes-sovereign-cloud-strategy/>

aligned with initiatives such as Gaia-X and Catena-X, which promote interoperable, federated data ecosystems.

4.2.2 The Role of Open Source in the European Union's Cloud and Edge Computing Strategy

OSS enables providers and public institutions to implement interoperable solutions and facilitates the creation of open standards for cross-border data and service exchange. European initiatives such as NeoNephos⁵², and Simpl⁵³ illustrate how open technologies can contribute to a federated and secure computing continuum that aligns with European regulatory and sustainability objectives. Series of EU Horizon projects including NexusForum.EU, CEI-Sphere, UNLOCK-CEI, and Open Continuum further emphasises the role OSS has to play in growing the continuum.

Another important initiative includes EuroStack⁵⁴, a bottom-up industry-driven and coordinated European initiative to establish a sovereign, interoperable, and competitive digital infrastructure, reducing reliance on foreign hyperscale providers such as AWS, Microsoft, and Google Cloud. Their core principles include Buy European (e.g., dedicated exceptions in public procurement), Sell European (e.g., common offerings from European cloud providers that matches hyperscalers), and Fund European (e.g., increased access to capital that can fund European SMEs and cloud vendors). OSS, as well as open and standardised APIs and interfaces are key enablers in the EuroStack strategy to enable vendor independence by ensuring that infrastructures and software components remain accessible, auditable, and adaptable within the European context.

Reports from the EU Open Source Policy Summit (2025) also emphasizes that open collaboration can reduce dependency on a limited number of external technology providers and facilitate innovation through shared development models⁵⁵. According to the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud⁵⁶, OSS approaches are instrumental in developing complete technological stacks— hardware to software orchestration—under initiatives such as EuroStack and IPCEI-CIS. These measures aim to strengthen Europe's technological sovereignty while promoting sustainable, standards-based ecosystems within its digital infrastructure.

4.2.3 The blending of top-down and bottom-up initiatives

Two of the most prominent initiatives, IPCEI-CIS and EuroStack, represents a top-down and bottom-up approach respectively towards growing sovereign and interoperable European Cloud capabilities.

⁵² <https://neonephos.org/>

⁵³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/simpl>

⁵⁴ <https://eurostack.eu/>

⁵⁵ <https://openforumeurope.org/the-eu-open-source-policy-summit-2025-what-did-we-learn-and-where-do-we-go-from-here/>

⁵⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cloud-alliance>

The IPCEI-CIS Reference Architecture defines a common blueprint based on eight layers—from physical infrastructure and network systems up to data, AI, and application layers—ensuring interoperability, scalability, and sustainability across distributed multi-provider environments. The framework’s purpose is to enable cross-border, next-generation digital services and strengthen Europe’s competitiveness and independence in cloud and edge computing. It provides a foundation for applications and neighbouring stacks to integrate with and build on, such as the Connected Collaborative Computing (3C)⁵⁷ which extends the IPCEI-CIS-defined building blocks and standards to telecom-integrated infrastructures and cross-domain orchestration, and them through deployment pilots across the connectivity and compute value chain.

EuroStack, in turn, promotes the creation of a federated cloud environment built upon open standards and shared governance to ensure interoperability, security, and compliance with EU data protection and sovereignty principles. However, there are no technical or architectural reference design provided. The intention is rather to leave the implementation to the industry to collaborate and agree on. An underpinning understanding, though, is that there is a need for common interfaces and building blocks that can allow for European cloud providers to integrate and create joint offerings that can compete with non-European hyperscalers, while also offering customers to ability to seamlessly switch between providers.

Both initiatives complement each other and align, taking a policy-driven top-down and an industry-driven bottom-up approach. Still, work needs to be done from both sides for avoiding duplicate efforts and to ensure a common path towards not just a demand and supply reality, but also towards the design and implementation of the open and interoperable standards and building blocks needed. Other efforts such as 8ra, NeoNephos and upcoming IPCEIs also need to be in alignment to ensure that efforts are kept general beyond the single interest of any country or company, or limited group thereof.

4.2.4 Facilitation and stewardship of open cloud development in Europe

The 8ra Initiative⁵⁸ is by some referred to as a central pillar in the EU’s digital sovereignty agenda under the IPCEI-CIS. Established through collaboration among twelve EU Member States and more than 120 industrial and research partners, 8ra seeks to create a resilient, interoperable, and secure multi-provider cloud-edge continuum. Its primary aim is to build a federated digital infrastructure that allows seamless data exchange and service integration across national and sectoral boundaries. The initiative promotes OSS development, transparent governance, and cross-border collaboration as mechanisms for strengthening Europe’s digital autonomy and reducing dependence on non-European platforms.

Within the broader 8ra framework, the NeoNephos Foundation, hosted by Linux Foundation Europe, functions as the OSS implementation layer supporting Europe’s sovereign cloud infrastructure. NeoNephos develops shared cloud-native components and governance models that

⁵⁷ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/HORIZON_HORIZON-CL4-2025-03-DATA-08

⁵⁸ <https://www.8ra.com/>

align with 8ra's objectives of interoperability and compliance. It provides an open environment where industrial members collaboratively design and maintain common cloud software components. Some criticism has been brought to NeoNephos being centred around the technology stacks donated by initial members, with less focus on the general European use case. Either way, the intention from involved parties is to enable autonomy by using open source as the lever.

4.3 Cybersecurity

4.3.1 Open Source as a medium for transparency and trust

Cybersecurity concerns the protecting computer systems, networks, devices, and data from unauthorized access, damage, or digital attacks. The practice employs a combination of technologies, processes, and policies. Its objective is to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information and services, thereby reducing the risk and impact of cyber threats on individuals and organizations.

In this context, OSS provides a medium and tool for enabling transparency, collaborative scrutiny, and rapid identification of vulnerabilities. This open model enables both defenders and attackers to examine tools, detection logic, and vulnerabilities, sometimes accelerating security advancements but also creating opportunities for malicious exploitation.

4.3.2 Commonly adopted means across cyber security agencies

According to a recent survey, a significant portion of organizations are investing in OSS security tools, while there is also a limited awareness to what extent such tools are used within the organizations. The narrow use cases, and by extension the limited user base may provide some explanations. Still, the importance is emphasized through several national agencies for cybersecurity and defence. Examples include the French Agency for Cyber Security (ANSSI) who has released a wide set of tools as OSS, as have also the Luxembourg House of Cybersecurity and the US Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA). ANSSI further highlights how they contribute to external key OSS projects including the Linux kernel and Debian, a GNU/Linux based operating system.

The French agency is also engaged in the Open Information Security Foundation, an OSS steward hosting security-oriented projects such as Suricata, an OSS network analysis and threat detection software. The Open Source Security Foundation (OpenSSF), part of the wider Linux Foundation, hosts a number of projects and initiatives focused on cybersecurity, while specifically focused on securing the development, maintenance, and consumption of the OSS.

4.3.3 Wide set of tools available for supporting developers

There is a vast ecosystem of various OSS projects in the domain. Some categories include Developer Best Practices, Fuzzing, Repository Security, Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) Tools, Software Supply Chain, Vulnerability disclosure, and Vulnerability scanning.

Tools focused on Developer Best Practices, help to promote, enforce, and follow-up such practices. Fuzz tools implement a dynamic analysis approach called fuzz testing where a large amount of input is generated and fed into the software to see how it responds. Network security and management tools focus on protection and mapping, monitoring, and analysing network activity. Repository Security tools provide a security layer for source code repositories. SBOM and vulnerability scanning tools in various ways enable the creation, use and analysis of SBOMs from upstream dependencies to a software. Software Supply Chain tools focus explicitly on creating

trust and transparency into the supply chain. Vulnerability disclosure tools enable vulnerability reporting and communication. Vulnerability scanning tools, scans for the presence of vulnerabilities in, e.g., repositories and networks.

4.4 Energy

4.4.1 Climate policy and the digital imperative

The energy sector is undergoing a profound transformation, driven by climate policy and the need for digital modernization. European initiatives such as the European Green Deal and the Fit for 55 package set ambitious targets for decarbonization—aiming for climate neutrality by 2050⁵⁹ and a 55% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 (compared to 1990 levels)⁶⁰. These goals necessitate a shift from centralised to distributed energy systems, increased electrification (e.g., through electric vehicles), and the integration of renewable energy sources.

This transition introduces significant technical challenges, including maintaining system stability, voltage control, and supply reliability⁶¹. The aging infrastructure of many European grids adds further complexity, requiring both replacement and optimization. To meet these demands, the sector must find clever ways in moving energy in smarter ways, and accelerate its digital transformation, with OSS playing a central role in enabling scalable, collaborative innovation.

4.4.2 Open Source as a strategic enabler

OSS is increasingly recognised as a strategic enabler of the energy transition. It supports the development of digital capabilities needed to manage complex, distributed energy systems and facilitates collaboration across national and organisational boundaries. Grid operators like Alliander, Energinet, Statnett, and RTE⁶² have embraced OSS not only to accelerate innovation but also to reduce duplication and cost by co-developing shared solutions.

A key factor compared to many other industries is that grid operators as RTE and Alliander have national monopolies, and are subject to similar regulatory requirements across countries, with similar tasks needing to be performed. Hence, there are many opportunities for collaboration and development of joint solutions, rather than developing parallel solutions, of buying same solution multiple times.

Collaboration and reuse are accordingly slowly moving towards increased share and reuse. While there is a general practice towards leveraging standard infrastructure components as Linux and Kubernetes, creation of Energy-domain specific solutions is low relative to other industries. Still, there are several projects emerging.

A recent study of 388 OSS projects in the energy domain⁶³, and several are hosted in LF Energy⁶⁴ reflects this shift, providing a neutral, transparent platform for collaborative development.

⁵⁹ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

⁶⁰ <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/fit-for-55/>

⁶¹ <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/16/16/5855>

⁶² <https://lfenergy.org/about/members/>

⁶³ <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/16/16/5855>

OpenSTEF⁶⁵, used for the forecasting of energy grid loads, and Power Grid Model⁶⁶, used for grid simulation in the distribution grid, are two prominent projects growing out of the increasing collaboration taking place in the industry. PowSyBl (Power System Blocks)⁶⁷ is another example, serving a wide range of power grid stakeholders across Europe, including transmission system operators and regional coordination centres, to build advanced grid analysis tools. A fourth case is that of Pandapower⁶⁸, OSS tool for power system modelling, analysis and optimization, is also highlighted as a key project.

4.4.3 From standardization to Software-Defined Infrastructure (SDI)

Traditional approaches to driving change—particularly through standardization—are increasingly seen as too slow and dominated by incumbents with limited incentives to innovate⁶⁹. The energy sector, characterised by its safety-critical nature and long investment cycles, has historically been conservative in adopting new technologies.

OSS offers an alternative path forward by enabling bottom-up interoperability and broader industry participation. This is especially relevant in the shift toward Software-Defined Infrastructure (SDI), which is emerging as a key paradigm for modernizing power grids and in enhancing their efficiency, resilience, and security.

Specifically, some of the potential of SDI includes the virtualization of operation, security and management of substations within the power grid, the collection and analysis of sensor data from across distribution and supply networks, support of automatic isolation and re-routing in the event of equipment failure or security issues, as well as improved operational efficiency and smart grid responsiveness, allowing utilities to modernise infrastructure effectively. OSS is viewed as essential to realizing this vision, enabling modular, adaptable, and secure digital infrastructure.

4.4.4 Collaboration and European leadership

Collaboration is central to the OSS model, and Europe is playing a leading role in shaping its application in the energy sector. LF Energy hosts a growing number of projects in areas such as grid automation, simulation, and operational management, with strong participation from European actors. Key contributors include RTE (France), Alliander (Netherlands), and smaller innovators like Pionix GmbH (Germany)⁷⁰, which focuses on OSS solutions for EV charging.

⁶⁴ <https://lfenergy.org/>

⁶⁵ <https://lfenergy.org/projects/openstef/>

⁶⁶ <https://lfenergy.org/projects/power-grid-model/>

⁶⁷ https://linuxfoundation.eu/hubfs/LF%20Europe%20Reports/lfeu_cs_powsybl_102125.pdf?hsLang=en

⁶⁸ <https://www.pandapower.org/>

⁶⁹ <https://lfenergy.org/view-from-the-community-challenges-to-the-digitalization-of-energy-systems/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.pionix.com/>

These collaborations are not only technical but also strategic. They reflect a shared recognition that OSS can support digital sovereignty, reduce dependency on non-European vendors, and foster a more resilient and competitive energy ecosystem. The presence of European actors in LF Energy projects ensures that regional needs and values are embedded in the development process.

4.4.5 Barriers to adoption and cultural shifts

Despite growing momentum, several barriers continue to hinder broader adoption of OSS in the energy sector. These include:

- Perceived legal and security risks, particularly around licensing and intellectual property.
- Lack of internal development capacity among many grid operators, who have traditionally relied on external vendors.
- Vendor resistance, as OSS threatens established business models based on proprietary systems.
- Cultural inertia, with many organisations unaccustomed to collaborative development and shared control.

RTE's and Alliander's experience illustrates how these barriers can be overcome. Legal reviews have shown that OSS licensing is compatible with public sector mandates, and internal development teams are beginning to emerge. There is also a growing recognition that traditional procurement models are failing to deliver the flexibility and innovation needed for real-time grid operations.

4.4.6 Linking research, industry, and operations

OSS is increasingly seen as a bridge between research and operational deployment. Projects funded under programs like Horizon Europe have historically struggled with industrialization and long-term sustainability. OSS offers a way to extend the impact of these projects by enabling continued development and reuse beyond the funding period.

RTE and Alliander advocate for stronger integration of OSS into EU research frameworks, including requirements for open licensing of publicly funded software. This would enhance transparency, reduce duplication, and support the creation of a shared digital infrastructure for the energy sector.

From the survey of 388 OSS projects in the energy domain, it was found that most are driven by academia, with limited industry engagement⁷¹. Strengthening collaboration between research institutions and operational actors is seen as essential for scaling innovation and ensuring practical relevance.

⁷¹https://git.rwth-aachen.de/acs/public/publications/2023-oss-in-energy-data/-/blob/master/projects.csv?ref_type=heads

4.4.7 Standardization and open ecosystems

Standardization remains essential for interoperability, but current processes are often misaligned with the pace and openness of OSS development. Many standards are locked behind paywalls or governed by restrictive IP regimes, limiting their accessibility and adaptability.

RTE and Alliander are advocating for a shift toward open standardization, where code and specifications are developed transparently and released under open licenses. This would enable faster adoption, greater innovation, and more inclusive participation. The convergence of standardization and software development—particularly in SDI contexts—makes this shift both necessary and timely.

The ongoing R&I initiative CRESYM⁷² is highlighted as an ongoing and successful example of industry-academia collaboration, when OSS is a key factor.

⁷² <https://cresym.eu/>

4.5 Healthcare

The accelerating pace of innovation in software technologies—particularly in artificial intelligence, data analytics, and digital infrastructure—is reshaping possibilities for healthcare systems. These technologies offer the potential to improve efficiency, enhance clinical decision-making, and enable more personalised care by leveraging vast and diverse health data. However, the realization of these benefits is contingent on the ability to exchange, access, and interpret data across systems and institutions—capabilities that remain constrained by structural, cultural, and regulatory barriers.

4.5.1 Fragmented competency and institutional silos

Healthcare continues to be characterised by siloed domains of expertise. Medical professionals are primarily focused on clinical care, often with limited engagement in technological innovation. Technologists, conversely, may lack the domain-specific knowledge required to design solutions that align with clinical workflows and regulatory constraints. This disconnect hinders the co-creation of effective digital health solutions and underscores the need for convergence between people, processes, and technologies.

In the UK, for example, NHS⁷³ reports that there is a relatively large digital workforce within healthcare, and many engineers and analysts actively embrace OSS principles. The Government Digital Service has promoted “open by default” policies, and individual practitioners often recognise the benefits of OSS. However, institutional adoption remains inconsistent. National ambitions and strategic goals frequently reference OSS, yet these aspirations rarely translate into sustained implementation. The gap between policy-level endorsement and operational uptake reflects broader tensions in healthcare governance.

OSS adoption is further complicated, in countries like Canada and Italy, by federated systems where healthcare delivery and decision-making are decentralised, with authority distributed across regional or provincial entities. Each region may establish its own priorities, procurement protocols, and technical standards, leading to fragmentation in how digital health initiatives are implemented. Even when national bodies articulate support for OSS, local institutions may lack the capacity, resources, or political will to follow through. This results in inconsistent adoption patterns, where some regions advance OSS initiatives while others remain reliant on proprietary systems.

4.5.2 Regulatory conservatism and procurement barriers

Healthcare is a safety-critical domain governed by complex regulatory frameworks. This leads to a conservative approach to innovation, particularly in public institutions. Developing software that meets regulatory, ethical, and safety standards is both time-consuming and costly, limiting the number of actors capable of contributing. Moreover, the lack of openness and interoperability in existing platforms makes integration difficult, especially for startups and smaller vendors.

⁷³ <https://www.england.nhs.uk/digitaltechnology/open-source/>

Concerns around licensing, liability, and security persist, even when technical teams are supportive. Senior management often remains cautious, particularly when OSS intersects with medical devices or grant-funded innovation. The regulatory landscape complicates the use of open licenses, especially when intellectual property rights are embedded in funding agreements. As projects move from conceptualization to implementation, legal and compliance concerns increasingly dominate, often stalling adoption.

4.5.3 The promise and complexity of Open Source Software

OSS offers a compelling alternative to proprietary systems by promoting transparency, interoperability, and community-driven development. These characteristics align well with the ethical and regulatory demands of healthcare, and OSS has the potential to support more equitable and sustainable digital health ecosystems. However, the adoption of OSS in healthcare—particularly in public institutions—remains limited. Risk aversion, entrenched procurement practices, and the influence of incumbent vendors and lobbyists continue to pose significant barriers.

The UK experience through the lens of NHS illustrates this tension. While there are successful examples of OSS in data science and internal applications—such as reproducible analytical pipelines and COVID-19 assessment tools—these are often limited in scope and scale. Hospitals tend to operate closed technology stacks, and OSS adoption in frontline clinical applications remains rare. For OSS projects that do exist, maintenance and sustainability are features as a key challenge, with many projects experiencing cycles of investment followed by neglect.

There are, however, some prominent examples of OSS projects in the healthcare sector that has reached wide adoption.

- DHIS2 (District Health Information Software 2)⁷⁴ is a health information management system used globally to collect, manage, and analyse health data. It is particularly prominent in public health and epidemiological surveillance, especially in low- and middle-income countries. The project is classified as a Digital Public Good and developed mainly with sponsorship from the University of Oslo.
- Imaging and visualization are other fields where OSS software provides solutions. One of these is 3D Slicer⁷⁵, which includes image analysis and scientific visualization tools. Medical professionals use it for various medical applications as diverse as autism, multiple sclerosis, systemic lupus erythematosus, prostate cancer, lung cancer, breast cancer, schizophrenia, orthopaedic biomechanics, COPD, cardiovascular disease, and neurosurgery.
- Orthanc⁷⁶ is a DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) server designed for medical imaging. It was created to make it easier for healthcare professionals, researchers,

⁷⁴ <https://dhis2.org/>

⁷⁵ <https://www.slicer.org/>

⁷⁶ <https://www.orthanc-server.com/>

and developers to manage and exchange medical images, particularly in environments where traditional Picture Archiving and Communication Systems (PACS) are too complex or costly.

- GNU Health⁷⁷ is an OSS initiative and hospital information system software suite under the Free Software Foundation designed to support public health care delivery, clinical management, and medical research. It is part of a broader movement to democratise access to digital health tools, especially in resource-constrained environments.

4.5.4 GNU Health and the global landscape

GNU Health provides an interesting example, both of the potential and the challenges of OSS in healthcare. Despite its technical maturity and compliance with standards such as GDPR, adoption in Europe has been slow. Legislative and institutional barriers—especially within public healthcare—make it difficult for institutions to adopt free software. The presence of strong lobbying interests in health informatics further complicates the landscape.

Nonetheless, GNU Health has found traction in academic and research settings. Institutions in Belgium, Spain, and Germany have integrated the platform into genomics research and health informatics education. Collaborations with universities such as the University of Hannover and the University of Leuven have supported both technical development and pedagogical use.

Outside Europe, adoption has been more widespread. In South America, particularly Argentina, over 50 projects have been launched since 2011, often initiated by academic institutions in partnership with local hospitals. These projects typically begin as pilots and, if successful, are scaled up and sustained independently. NGOs have also played a key role, using GNU Health in contexts such as migrant health and mental health care. For example, a mental health institution in Valencia uses the platform for both clinical care and patient management.

Private companies have contributed by implementing GNU Health in specialised contexts, such as cancer treatment labs, and by contributing code and ideas to the broader community. One notable example involves a Dutch NGO using GNU Health to facilitate electronic health transactions via cryptocurrency protocols. These diverse use cases illustrate the flexibility and adaptability of OSS in addressing varied healthcare needs.

4.5.5 Towards sustainable and inclusive innovation

While OSS remains a niche within the broader healthcare IT landscape, its potential to foster innovation, transparency, and sustainability is increasingly recognised. Projects like GNU Health, Orthanc, and DHIS2 illustrate the value of collaborative, community-driven approaches to digital health. Realizing this potential at scale will require not only technical solutions but also cultural and institutional change—particularly in how public institutions procure and evaluate software. Pilot projects, academic partnerships, and sustained advocacy will be key to bridging the gap between vision and implementation.

⁷⁷ <https://www.gnuhealth.org/>

The future of OSS in healthcare may depend less on overcoming technical barriers and more on navigating institutional inertia, regulatory complexity, and funding structures. As open standards and data sharing continue to gain ground, the challenge will be to extend these principles to application development and long-term maintenance. With the right support, OSS can become a cornerstone of more open, equitable, and resilient healthcare systems.

4.6 Smart Cities

Smart cities are urban environments where digital technologies are deployed to deliver more efficient services, reduce emissions, and optimise the management of resources such as energy, water, waste, and buildings. These technologies also enhance governance by integrating citizen needs and feedback into administrative processes. Citizen engagement is a central element, supported by mobile applications, social media, and other digital channels. OSS technologies are increasingly significant, as they provide cost-effective, flexible, and collaborative solutions that support innovation and transparency.

4.6.1 Core technologies and the role of IoT

A core technological foundation of smart cities is the Internet of Things (IoT), which refers to devices equipped with sensors, software, and connectivity that enable data exchange with other devices and systems. These “things” range from consumer products such as smart thermostats and wearable trackers to industrial machinery and municipal infrastructure components. IoT’s goal is to improve efficiency, accuracy, and economic value by leveraging automation and data-driven insights.

Due to the modular and distributed nature of IoT, open standards are critical for ensuring interoperability among devices and networks. Many of these standards are supported by OSS implementations, notably through the FIWARE Foundation and its FIWARE platform, which provides a suite of OSS components used either in their original form or as the basis for commercial services. A central element is the Orion Context Broker, which enables real-time contextual data management and exchange between system components. These building blocks are commonly implemented within IoT platforms offered by various providers, available either as fully OSS distributions or integrated into proprietary offerings. For local governments—often key stakeholders in smart city initiatives—commercial support becomes essential, as many lack the technical capacities to manage complex OSS solutions independently.

IoT also intersects with the establishment of European Data Spaces, designed to ensure secure, efficient, and interoperable data exchange across sectors. Initiatives such as FIWARE contribute connectors that comply with standards like ETSI NGSI-LD, which defines APIs for contextual data exchange. Similarly, the Eclipse Foundation develops the Eclipse Dataspace Connector, part of its broader engagement with OSS projects in the IoT domain. These connectors play an essential role in enabling trusted data sharing across different stakeholders and infrastructures, a prerequisite for achieving data sovereignty and cross-border interoperability in European smart city contexts.

4.6.2 Stakeholders and governance

Smart city development involves a broad spectrum of actors. Citizens and community groups benefit directly from services and provide feedback essential for improvement. Governments at the local, regional, and national levels establish policy frameworks, provide funding, and ensure compliance with legal standards, particularly in areas such as privacy and sustainability. The private sector supplies infrastructure and services, while academic institutions contribute

research-driven innovation and methodological support. NGOs and advocacy groups play a role in ensuring inclusivity and ethical application, complemented by the involvement of international organisations and standardization bodies that promote best practices and technical harmonization. Investors and financial institutions provide vital capital, often through public–private partnerships. Finally, urban planners and architects ensure that digital infrastructures are integrated into urban design in a sustainable and citizen-centred manner.

4.6.3 Skills and competences

The interdisciplinary nature of smart cities requires expertise in programming, data analytics, IoT protocols, and cloud computing, alongside practices such as DevOps and continuous integration. Equally important are non-technical domains, including urban planning, governance, data ethics, and citizen engagement. The rollout of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, distributed ledger technologies, 5G/6G, and smart grids further reinforces the importance of continual skill development within municipalities and among service providers.

4.6.4 Sustained support

Smart city infrastructures rely on ongoing technical, organisational, and social support. This includes cybersecurity measures, data analysis, and system maintenance, but also long-term strategies for citizen involvement and transparency. Sustained research and funding are essential to ensure adaptability and the continued relevance of technological solutions in response to evolving urban challenges.

4.6.5 Benefits and challenges with Open Source technologies

OSS technologies bring significant advantages for cities, offering cost savings, adaptability, interoperability, and access to large developer communities that drive innovation. Yet, barriers remain. Security vulnerabilities, the need for long-term support, scalability challenges in large deployments, and integration with legacy systems are persistent issues. Moreover, limited expertise within municipal administrations can hinder adoption. Addressing these barriers is essential if cities are to maximize the benefits of OSS solutions and build smart urban environments that are efficient, inclusive, and sustainable.

4.7 Transportation

4.7.1 Mobility, climate, and digital transformation

The European transport sector is undergoing rapid change driven by climate policy, digital transformation, and the EU's ambition for sustainable, smart mobility. Decarbonisation targets under the European Green Deal require electrification, modal shifts, and greater integration of transport networks. The rise of electric vehicles (EVs), digital logistics, and multimodal journey planning adds complexity to an already fragmented ecosystem. Achieving interoperability across borders and systems is essential both to meet climate goals and to strengthen Europe's competitiveness.

4.7.2 Future charging capabilities for electric vehicles

OSS is increasingly recognised as a strategic enabler for transport. It underpins interoperability in EV charging (e.g. Everest, hosted by LF Energy, developed by Pionix) to avoid stranded assets and future-proof charging infrastructure. In freight and logistics, the Open Logistics Foundation develops shared OSS components for warehouse and transport management systems, reducing duplication and dependency on proprietary vendors. Rail operators such as Deutsche Bahn (DB) and SNCF are also turning to OSS as part of their digital strategies.

OSS underpins much of the cloud and IT infrastructure in transport but is only beginning to penetrate domain-specific systems. Railway operators rely heavily on sector-specific software for network management, scheduling, and simulation—often fragmented across national borders and subject to regulatory divergence. Here, OSS offers a way to pool resources, avoid duplicative investments, and create shared solutions across Europe.

4.7.3 Opening up the design and infrastructure of the European railway

The formation of the Open Rail Association in 2023 exemplifies this shift. It brings together rail operators to co-develop sector-specific OSS, inspired by earlier moves in energy and automotive. One flagship example is SNCF's Open Railway Designer, a simulation tool that models network topologies and scenarios such as optimizing energy use or testing infrastructure upgrades. By releasing it as OSS, SNCF sought broader adoption and integration, spurring collaboration with DB and others.

Other projects include planning software for the large-scale European migration to digital automatic coupling in freight trains—where German government funding incentivised open sourcing for sustainability beyond project lifetimes. Such examples highlight how OSS can act both as an efficiency measure (sharing development costs) and as a means of ensuring public investments remain accessible to all operators. Interview insights confirm this shift: OSS is seen as a way to regain digital sovereignty and reduce lock-in, though procurement frameworks and internal capacity remain barriers.

4.8 Telecommunications

The European telecommunications industry is undergoing a significant transformation in its relationship with OSS and OSH. Once peripheral to the sector's core operations, OSS is now central to how networks are designed, built, and operated. Major European operators—including Deutsche Telekom, Orange, and Telecom Italia—are actively contributing to and adopting OSS projects such as OpenAirInterface (OAI), OpenStack, and initiatives under the Open Networking Foundation (ONF). This shift is driven by a combination of technological necessity, economic pressure, and policy support.

The European Commission has played a catalytic role in this transition. Through instruments like the 5G Toolbox and the European Open Science Cloud, it has promoted open standards and OSS adoption as vehicles for innovation, sovereignty, and security. As a result, OSS is increasingly seen not just as a cost-saving measure, but as a strategic enabler of agility, interoperability, and vendor independence.

4.8.1 Embedded use, strategic gaps

Across the industry, OSS is deeply embedded in product development. Vendors such as Nokia and Ericsson incorporate OSS components into nearly all modern solutions, from operating systems to orchestration frameworks. The transition from proprietary platforms to OSS foundations—particularly Linux and Kubernetes—has become standard practice. However, this integration is often tactical. OSS is used extensively, but long-term strategic planning around OSS engagement remains underdeveloped.

This reflects a broader cultural and structural gap. Telecom has traditionally been hardware-centric, and while software development capabilities have matured, the sector still lacks a deep understanding of the broader software ecosystem. OSS is frequently consumed as a tool, rather than embraced as a collaborative process. This limits the industry's ability to influence upstream projects or build sustainable communities around telecom-specific needs.

4.8.2 Compliance and Intellectual Property

Legal and intellectual property considerations further complicate OSS adoption. Telecom vendors must navigate both OSS license compliance and the protection of standard-essential patents. For companies with significant IPR-based revenue streams, this creates a delicate balance. Contributions to OSS must be carefully managed to avoid disclosing proprietary technologies. Licensing models such as that used by the OpenAirInterface Software Alliance reflect an effort to reconcile collaborative development with the commercial realities of telecom R&D.

4.8.3 Structural constraints and community limitations

The telecom industry's relatively small size poses a fundamental challenge to OSS engagement. While it may appear large from within, it is modest compared to ecosystems surrounding projects like Linux or Kubernetes. Telecom-specific initiatives often struggle to attract broad participation and attempts to build dedicated communities frequently fall short.

This is compounded by a belief that telecom is uniquely complex. The sector often assumes its requirements are too specialised for general-purpose solutions, leading to bespoke approaches that isolate it from broader trends. While telecom does have distinct performance and lifecycle demands, this perception can become self-limiting, discouraging collaboration and reuse.

Standardization remains the dominant mode of industrial coordination. organisations like 3GPP have enabled global interoperability and long-term planning, but their structured processes contrast sharply with the iterative, community-driven nature of OSS. OSS is still seen as an outsider in a system where industrialization has traditionally meant formal standards.

4.8.4 Long product life cycles and fragmented demand

The product lifecycle in telecom further complicates OSS integration. Networks are deployed for decades, and any disruption can have serious consequences. Unlike cloud-native companies that iterate rapidly, telecom vendors and operators operate on multi-year timelines. This affects everything from software release cycles to upgrade strategies.

The separation between vendors and operators adds another layer of complexity. Operators are powerful but highly individualised customers. Each has specific requirements, and vendors must tailor their products accordingly. This leads to significant fragmentation and limits the potential for shared solutions. While there is technical collaboration, the responsibility for network operation lies firmly with the operator, who selects, deploys, and maintains the systems. Vendors support these deployments but do not control them.

4.8.5 Skills shortage and organisational barriers

A critical barrier to OSS adoption is the shortage of skilled professionals. The telecom industry requires expertise in software development, networking protocols, and system integration to effectively adopt OSS and OSH. Yet 93% of companies⁷⁸ report difficulty in finding talent with the necessary OSS skills. This shortage slows down the pace of innovation and complicates efforts to build internal capacity for OSS engagement.

organisational inertia also plays a role. Many telcos have long relied on proprietary solutions and may be hesitant to adopt OSS alternatives due to concerns about security, reliability, and support. Transitioning to OSS often requires significant changes in how networks are designed, built, and operated—a complex and time-consuming process that can encounter resistance at multiple levels.

4.8.6 Enablers and emerging ecosystems

Despite these challenges, several enablers are driving OSS adoption. The growing ecosystem of OSS communities and projects provides a wealth of knowledge, expertise, and resources.

⁷⁸The Linux Foundation. (2022). "2022 Open Source Jobs Report". Retrieved from the Linux Foundation website.

Initiatives like the Open Networking Foundation (ONF)⁷⁹ and the Telecom Infra Project (TIP)⁸⁰, with hundreds of member companies, are fostering collaboration and lowering barriers to entry.

Projects such as OpenAirInterface⁸¹, ONAP⁸², and Nephio⁸³ are gaining traction, particularly in areas like 5G, edge computing, and network functions virtualization (NFV). LF Networking plays a pivotal role in facilitating many of the industry-specific collaborations. AI is another domain where OSS is becoming indispensable. Most AI frameworks and models are OSS or claim to be, introducing new challenges around compliance and reproducibility. The Open Source AI (OSAI) definition is one effort to clarify how software principles apply to AI artifacts.

4.8.7 Europe's strategic position

Europe remains a global leader in telecom innovation. Vendors such as Nokia and Ericsson dominate mobile infrastructure markets outside of China and Africa, and the region continues to lead in research and standardization. The European Commission's support for OSS and open standards has reinforced this position, aligning industrial policy with technological sovereignty.

However, the industry has undergone significant consolidation. Where once there were many players—Alcatel, Lucent, Siemens, Nortel, Motorola—now only a few remain. This has increased pressure on margins and reduced the diversity of perspectives in the ecosystem. China, through companies like Huawei and ZTE, has emerged as a strong competitor, while U.S.-based firms have less presence in mobile infrastructure.

⁷⁹<https://opennetworking.org>

⁸⁰<https://telecominfraproject.com>

⁸¹www.openairinterface.org

⁸²<https://www.onap.org>

⁸³[Nephio – Linux Foundation Project](#)

4.9 Manufacturing

The European manufacturing industry is undergoing a profound transformation characterised by the integration of digital technologies and the broader adoption of Industry 4.0 principles. Within this context, OSH and OSS are gaining strategic importance. Manufacturers are increasingly drawn to the flexibility, scalability, and cost advantages offered by OSS solutions, which allow them to respond more dynamically to competitive pressures and technological change. Although notable examples of successful adoption already exist, OSS technologies in European manufacturing remain in an early stage of broader uptake, with considerable potential for further development.

4.9.1 Key stakeholders and projects

The transition toward OSS adoption is being shaped by a diverse network of stakeholders, including established industrial players, startups, research organisations, and government-backed initiatives. European projects and consortia focused on OSHW and OSS are central to this ecosystem, fostering collaborative innovation and providing frameworks that enable shared development of tools, platforms, and industrial applications.

4.9.2 Skills and competences

The successful implementation of OSS solutions in manufacturing depends on a combination of technical and organisational skills. On the hardware side, competencies such as electronic circuit design, PCB layout, embedded systems, CAD-based modelling, and expertise in additive and subtractive manufacturing technologies are crucial. Software-related expertise includes proficiency in programming languages such as Python and Java, familiarity with OSS development frameworks, experience with data analytics and machine learning, as well as knowledge of cloud platforms, DevOps practices, and cybersecurity standards. Beyond technical skills, business-oriented and collaborative capabilities are equally important, including agile development methodologies, engagement in OSS communities, and the capacity to adapt to emerging business models.

4.9.3 Support needs

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), especially those in traditional industries such as metalworking and textiles, are among the actors most in need of targeted support to adopt OSHW and OSS. Many face challenges in developing digital skills or integrating new technologies into legacy production processes. Industry clusters and regional networks benefit from structures that facilitate knowledge-sharing and dissemination of best practices, while startups and OSS solution developers require access to funding, partnerships, and clear regulatory pathways. Support measures therefore include R&D funding, tailored education and training programs, collaborative networks, and innovation-friendly policy frameworks that encourage OSS adoption.

4.9.4 Enablers, challenges, and barriers

Several enablers foster the uptake of OSS technologies in manufacturing, including advances in digital and industrial technologies, collaborative innovation, cost advantages, flexibility, and

growing support through European policies. At the same time, significant barriers remain. These include a lack of awareness within the sector, technical and organisational complexity, concerns regarding scalability, reliability, and cybersecurity, as well as gaps in standardization and persistent questions around intellectual property and licensing models. Addressing these issues requires targeted investment in skills and infrastructure, business model adaptation, and access to robust support and maintenance systems.

4.9.5 Impact, sustainability, and recognition

The adoption of OSH and OSS in manufacturing has the potential to deliver substantial impacts. These include higher efficiency and productivity levels, better quality and customization of products, cost reductions, and accelerated innovation cycles. Ensuring the long-term sustainability of OSS solutions depends on maintaining active community engagement, continued commitment from industrial partners and vendors, and investment in skills development and infrastructure. Recognition and legitimacy can be reinforced through certification and testing procedures, adherence to standards, community-based validation, and supportive government incentives.

4.10 Automotive

The automotive sector is undergoing a significant transition from a hardware-oriented production paradigm toward one increasingly dominated by software components. The emergence of software-defined vehicles (SDVs) reflects this development, where functionality and performance are increasingly governed by updatable and connected software systems. Open source software (OSS) constitutes an important element in this transition by enabling collaborative innovation, promoting interoperability, and mitigating the challenges associated with technological fragmentation.

At present, the degree of OSS integration varies across automotive subsystems. It is more prevalent in development tools, backend systems, and infotainment, while adoption in safety-critical in-vehicle contexts remains limited due to certification requirements and liability considerations. Nevertheless, empirical evidence suggests a gradual increase in OSS use as companies recognize its potential for cost-efficiency, innovation, and knowledge exchange within a regulated framework.

4.10.1 Transition towards a decoupled and interoperable SDV platform

The gradual consolidation of distributed electronic control units (ECUs) into centralized computing architectures represents a key structural evolution within contemporary vehicles. This shift supports the development of unified yet modular platforms that can host interoperable building blocks with standardized interfaces. The envisaged SDV platform is based on open standards and aims to ensure seamless integration of both real-time and general-purpose operating environments through virtualization and containerization technologies.

Although a fully implemented SDV platform has not been realized, several coordinated initiatives indicate a move toward shared architectural frameworks. Collaborative fora, such as the Eclipse Software Defined Vehicle Working Group, AUTOSAR Adaptive, and COVESA, demonstrate industry efforts to advance interoperable solutions under open governance. These initiatives suggest that progress in platform standardization will likely depend on collective agreement regarding interface standardization rather than the dominance of individual proprietary systems.

4.10.2 Technological advancements pushing software complexity

Advances in electrification, autonomous driving, and connectivity have substantially increased vehicle software complexity. As software lines of code multiply and functionalities expand, individual firms face challenges maintaining control over integration and system safety. Cross-organizational OSS collaboration provides a mechanism to distribute development costs, maintain interoperability, and establish common technical baselines.

The ongoing development of high-performance computing frameworks and vehicle-to-cloud architectures further reinforces the need for standardized software practices. Collaborative structures, such as the Eclipse SDV Working Group and the ELISA project, exemplify attempts to align OSS with functional safety requirements. The availability of shared components and

verification frameworks is expected to support both innovation and regulatory compliance across the European automotive sector.

4.10.3 Safety-critical and conservative industry

Automotive manufacturing remains constrained by the safety-critical nature of its products and associated regulatory requirements. Certification standards, notably ISO 26262, impose rigorous development, testing, and traceability processes that can limit OSS adoption in embedded environments. The long operational lifespan of vehicles further accentuates the need for stable and predictable software maintenance strategies.

Despite these constraints, there is increasing recognition that structured OSS governance can coexist with safety-oriented methodologies. Initiatives addressing certification alignment, such as ELISA, illustrate how open source development processes can be adapted for compliance with functional safety regimes. The integration of transparent and verifiable OSS frameworks may provide a basis for enhancing long-term maintainability without compromising system integrity.

4.10.4 Need of up-skilling and talent acquisition

The shift toward software-defined mobility increases the demand for specialized software development expertise across the automotive value chain. Organizations face challenges in recruiting and retaining talent with competencies spanning systems engineering, software architecture, and OSS management. Engagement in open source ecosystems has been identified as a strategy to enhance organizational attractiveness for developers and engineers seeking collaborative and technologically current workplaces.

Open Source Program Offices (OSPOs) have emerged as an institutional instrument to support this transition. These units coordinate OSS governance, manage legal compliance, and promote knowledge development within firms. Their broader role extends to fostering culture change by integrating open collaboration practices into established corporate structures. Empirical observations indicate that OSPOs contribute not only to risk management but also to strategic capability building.

4.10.5 Moving from a hierarchical towards ecosystem structure

The hierarchical supply model that traditionally characterizes the automotive industry is increasingly challenged by the demands of software integration and cross-organizational interdependence. The emergence of OSS-based collaborations supports a transition toward networked ecosystems where actors co-develop shared infrastructure and standards. Collaborations such as Automotive Grade Linux, AUTOSAR, and Catena-X illustrate the move toward such interconnected ecosystems.

Adopting an ecosystem structure requires adjustments in governance and intellectual property management. Cooperative engagement in pre-competitive domains allows participants to focus resources on differentiated innovation layers. This form of collaboration aligns with the principle of modular co-creation, balancing openness and competition in the development of SDV-related technologies.

4.10.6 Key role of governments in facilitating and sponsoring industry collaboration

Public authorities play a significant role in facilitating cross-sector collaboration in automotive software development. By offering neutral convening platforms and targeted funding, governments can mitigate coordination and competition barriers among industrial actors. The European Commission has taken a notable position in promoting such initiatives through programs supporting open technological infrastructures.

Funding mechanisms and policy guidance help align industrial innovation with regulatory and strategic objectives, particularly concerning interoperability, security, and sustainability. Governmental involvement can thus be considered an enabling factor that supports the establishment of collaborative frameworks while maintaining compliance with safety and data protection standards.

4.10.7 Functional safety and long product lifespan require new OSS practice

The coexistence of OSS and safety-certified systems introduces requirements for long-term maintainability and controlled dependency management. Automotive software must remain operational and secure throughout the vehicle lifecycle, often spanning several decades. This necessitates systematic approaches to long-term support and lifecycle coordination across multiple project stakeholders.

Emerging models of OSS maintenance—such as foundation-led stewardship and standardized certification frameworks—aim to address these extended obligations. The integration of traceability, configuration management, and continuous assurance processes is becoming essential to sustain reliability across evolving technological environments.

4.10.8 An open SDV platform key for a sovereign and competitive European Automotive industry

An open and interoperable SDV platform is a prerequisite for ensuring strategic autonomy and competitiveness within the European automotive sector. Dependence on proprietary systems risks limiting regional control over key technologies and standards. The development of open platforms based on OSS can reduce such dependencies while fostering industrial collaboration across multiple layers of the value chain.

A shared platform model governed by open principles enables coordination on common technological foundations while preserving differentiation at higher-value layers. This approach supports regulatory alignment, promotes transparency, and contributes to maintaining Europe's competitive position in global automotive software development.

4.11 Agriculture

Agriculture in Europe provides 20 million jobs and supplies 500 million consumers with food and stocks⁸⁴. Requirements on increased efficiencies and sustainability, balanced with a changing climate, limited margins and resources, highlights the need to explore and leverage the potential of collaborative development and sharing of digital technology that can help transform the sector.

4.11.1 Increasing lock-in to Agribusinesses and Big Tech

This change is, however, being slowed down as farmers and companies in the sector are, along with their data, becoming increasingly locked into silos and proprietary systems owned and governed large international Agribusinesses and Big Tech⁸⁵. The latter are reported as showing limited interest in interoperability and data portability outside of their respective ecosystems. The lock-in is also reported further down in the supply-chain, as the sellers, who procure the farmers' outputs, is also dominated by incumbents.

4.11.2 Majority small scale farmers with limited resources and interest

Interest and capabilities to experiment and adopt new solutions, such as OSS-based differs across the sector. The small percentage of big farmers who dominate in the countries such as France, the Netherlands, and east Europe are described as resourceful and tech savvy. Smaller farmers, which constitutes the majority in Europe, are in opposite less savvy and have much more limited resources. The limited interest can be explained by an emotional connection to and focus on the practice and culture of farming family land through generations, implying less concern about market and technology trends.

4.11.3 Limited funding for investments and innovation

The limited resources and interest among farmers further strengthen the lock-in effects, and also by extent limiting the general opportunities for investments into OSS technology in general. One interviewee describes how there is “No money in Agri[culture]” compared to other sectors, and how “the big players who have the margins... are happy in buying from big suppliers”.

4.11.4 Public research funding and subsidies as enablers

Research funding, subsidies and requirements on OSS dissemination is seen as a main driver for the use and development of OSS in agriculture. Research outputs, however, struggle with large sustainability issues, and OSS projects becoming abandoned after research funding stops. Still,

⁸⁴ <https://op.europa.eu/publication-detail/-/publication/f08f5f20-ef62-11e6-8a35-01aa75ed71a1>

⁸⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517241306365>

there are several projects reported on, both in OSS and OSH⁸⁶, addressing use cases such as Automation and Robotics, Farm Management Systems, and Remote Sensing and Imagery⁸⁷.

⁸⁶ <https://horizon-openagri.eu/open-source-catalogue/>

⁸⁷ <https://github.com/brycejohnston/awesome-agriculture>

5 Cross-case analysis on Open Source Hardware

Below, we provide a broader and overarching analysis of the challenges and opportunities across OSH from the different lenses of legal, business, policy, development, and governance. We accordingly propose specific aspects and types of contributions that are of specific importance to invest in, as well as to recognise and promote to help foster OSH adoption in the EU, and by extension helping to advance its sovereignty and competitiveness in the global setting.

5.1 The legal perspective

5.1.1 OSH licencing and IP frameworks complex

While software open licensing (e.g., GPL, MIT) is well established, hardware licensing maturity lags behind, with varying use of the CERN Open Hardware License (OHL) as a leading option. A key difference is that OSH covers a complex set of potential artifacts and components, including (but not limited to) software, bill of materials, design files, assembly instructions, tool settings, etc. One interviewee makes the analogy that while software essentially comprises of ones and zeros, hardware comprises of atoms making the legal regimes that apply more complex. Ensuring that all information required of an OSH project to confirm with the definition is not an easy task.

Legal uncertainty surrounds the reuse of open mechanical designs or electronics that still depend on proprietary firmware or patented components. Projects such as Arduino balance openness and intellectual property by making designs open but protecting trademarks. In Arduino's case, the use of Creative Commons licenses was justified by the nature of the design files—stored as readable XML text—which resembled creative works more than executable code. This approach allowed for copying and modification of board designs without legal ambiguity.

A criticism towards the choice of Creative Commons licenses raised by one interviewee is that these licenses do not state anything about patents. All modern OSH licences contain a clause in which the licensor promises the licensees that they will not sue them for patent infringement. Creative Commons further does not recommend its licenses be used hardware (or software)⁸⁸.

5.1.2 Standards and certification efforts for assessing openness

OSHWA⁸⁹ maintains a certification program where communities can submit their projects and have them reviewed for conformance with the definition. A catalogue presents all OSH projects that have undergone this certification process. Yet, ensuring full compliance is difficult why the association considers itself more as an intermediary that does an initial assessment but fall back on the wider OSH ecosystem to verify or report if any OSH project does not comply with the definition.

⁸⁸ <https://choosealicense.com/non-software/>

⁸⁹ <https://OSHWA.org>

To improve compliance and transparency, an official standard was developed through community efforts involving 30+ organisations under the umbrella of the German Government's Standards Body. The DIN SPEC 3105⁹⁰ is described by one interviewee as a meta data standard highlighting minimum level requirements for the various artifacts and components of an OSH project. The standard also comes with a checklist for how conformance with the various requirements can be assessed. The standard is in itself open source available for community feedback. Adoption is unclear but does hands-on support for procurement and risk assessment when assessing whether to adopt or engage in an OSH project.

5.1.3 Enforcing license conditions difficult due to mix of legal regimes

The mix in types of artifacts present in OSH projects, also bring an equal mix of legal regimes to consider. One interviewee makes the analogy to Open Source AI where access to the full bundle is needed to truly understand and replicate the project. In OSS, everything is typically protected by copyright and controlled via license. In hardware and AI, some parts are protected by IP and others are not. This variability means creators have less control over downstream users, and the legal enforceability of obligations is more limited.

In software, the moment a developer writes code, it's protected. The developer can release it under a GPL license, and if someone copies it, the developer has legal recourse. In hardware, if someone copies a 3D printer design, the original designer often cannot force compliance. In some cases, licenses in OSH serve more as social signals than enforceable legal tools per one interviewee.

5.1.4 Structural miss-match and non-transferable regional certification schemes

OSH faces a fundamental clash with existing certification systems like CE and FCC, which assume a single manufacturer controls and documents every production step. OSH designs, by contrast, are made for remixing and distributed fabrication. Because certifications are non-transferable, even minor design or material changes require fresh compliance testing, making replication costly and discouraging small or community manufacturers from reusing open designs.

This issue is especially problematic in regulated domains such as healthcare, automotive, and aerospace, where safety and quality assurance are prerequisites for market entry. While OSH's openness enhances transparency and potential reproducibility, the inability to reuse or extend certifications undermines these advantages. The result is a systemic mismatch: open collaboration depends on shared access, yet certification frameworks are built for closed, single-origin production. Reforms enabling transferable or modular certification pathways are therefore crucial for the sustainable scaling of Europe's open hardware ecosystem.

⁹⁰ <https://www.din.de/resource/blob/721286/e726e17c7ffef0b155cdc693e00a4a6/broschuere-din-spec-3105-data.pdf>

5.1.5 Technology Transfer Offices both a bottleneck and enabler for OSH

European Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) remain a structural barrier to expanding OSH within research ecosystems due to their continued focus on proprietary IP strategies. Historically incentivized by patenting and revenue-generation targets, TTOs tend to treat patents and exclusive licenses as the default instruments of technology valorisation. This orientation discourages open dissemination, delaying releases and limiting the collaborative potential of publicly funded research. For OSH, whose value lies in openness, reuse, and shared improvement, the insistence on exclusivity often obstructs innovation rather than protecting it. Researchers motivated to release their work openly frequently face institutional resistance, bureaucratic delays, or mandates to pursue protection first.

This bias stands in contrast to evolving EU policy priorities that emphasise knowledge valorisation through openness. EU frameworks increasingly promote open sharing of publicly funded outputs to accelerate innovation, reduce dependency on proprietary ecosystems, and align with the European Research Area's open science agenda. The findings show early examples of alignment through academic Open Source Program Offices (OSPOs), which reinterpret technology transfer as a process of building transparent, collaborative, and sustainable innovation capacity rather than protecting IP. Such offices complement and often integrate with TTOs by supporting open licensing, documentation, and community partnerships—offering a potential model for reconciling open hardware dissemination with institutional mandates for accountability and impact.

5.1.6 Recommendations for public policy and recognition efforts

Based on the synthesised findings, we recommend public policy to prioritise investments, but also public recognition efforts such as the European Open Source Awards to highlight significant contributions made, into:

- Clarifying and simplifying OSH licensing practices to accommodate diverse artifacts, materials, and design components across mechanical, electronic, and software domains.
- Developing and adopting transparent, verifiable standards that help assess and certify the openness and compliance of OSH projects.
- Strengthening the legal enforceability and interoperability of OSH licenses across overlapping IP regimes and artifact types.
- Bridging the structural gap between OSH's distributed production model and rigid, single-manufacturer safety and compliance frameworks such as CE and FCC.
- Transforming Technology Transfer Offices from patent-centric units into facilitators of open licensing, collaborative research, and publicly reusable hardware outputs.

5.2 The business perspective

5.2.1 Certifications and implementation-specific details enabler for OSH business models

While the OSH definition and DIN SPEC 3105 calls for the source to be released in a form that can easily be modified, openness can still be limited, e.g., to implementation-specific elements such as

manufacturing processes or license requirements for specific components required. Arduino provides as example where the design is freely available, and any user is free to manufacture it. However, if user wishes to incorporate proprietary standards such as USB and Bluetooth into the Arduino boards, the boards either must be bought from Arduino, or the user must acquire its own official vendor ID from the USB and Bluetooth Special Interest Groups and license the number of component IDs necessary.

5.2.2 Culture and knowledge on OSH business models and opportunities limited

There is a general lack of culture and understanding of how OSH can be leveraged as an enabler for business models and generating revenue streams accordingly. In OSS, several models have been established, e.g., in providing support, customisation and maintenance; hosting and Software-as-a-Service offerings, and various open core models where the OSS is packaged. Similar models need to be explored and established also for the OSH context.

A critical aspect is where to draw the line between differentiating, enabling, and commodity technology. Opening commodity parts can enable many of the opportunities and cost efficacies of open innovation, while enabling a shift of focus to differentiating parts, building on the competitive edge for the company. By also driving the commoditisation of enabling technologies, and parts that will soon loose in differentiating value, a company can grow a leadership and drive the market per their own agenda.

For SMEs, challenges are accentuated further in the OSH context where the need of capital and funding is crucial to accelerate beyond seed-funding stages. They need to be enabled to enter the market on more fair terms with incumbents which typically dominate corporate-intensive projects such as the OCP project, and the related market. Developing knowledge and practice of OSH-based business models is an important step forward.

5.2.3 Growing a culture and practice of sharing and collaboration

The collaborative model in Chinese manufacturing, sometimes referred to as “Shensai,” is characterised by a culture where sharing of blueprints and rapid copying are widespread and copyright enforcement differs significantly from European practice. Rather than relying solely on restrictive intellectual property regimes, Chinese manufacturers and developers often operate in a context where the open exchange of technical knowledge is normalised. This environment encourages collaboration and speed, enabling actors to iterate quickly and apply competitive price pressure, which accelerates product releases and market entry.

The widespread availability of technical skills, combined with strong social networks, supports this rapid cycle of knowledge diffusion and joint development. The result is an adaptive ecosystem in which collaboration takes precedence over strict copyright protection, allowing for rapid scaling and innovation, especially within Chinese-language and manufacturing contexts. These dynamics highlight a potential opportunity for the European OSH community to similarly benefit from a culture of open exchange and collaboration to promote faster iteration and innovation.

5.2.4 Skills shortage enforced by structural barriers to entry

Europe's semiconductor and OSH industries face a severe shortage of skilled engineers in disciplines such as IC design, process engineering, and EDA tool development—an estimated gap exceeding 100,000 professionals. This deficit reflects structural issues in higher education and limited exposure to practical chip design, compounded by demographic turnover and competition from other tech sectors. The result is a bottleneck for innovation and sustainability, particularly for SMEs and research institutions dependent on open tools and collaborative workflows. While leading universities like ETH Zürich and TU Delft maintain strong programs, their scale cannot meet Europe's industrial targets under the European Chips Act.

Addressing this requires coupling education reform with open source strategies to democratize training and experimentation. Initiatives such as Edu4Chip and the European Chips Skills Academy (ECSA) demonstrate how modular, hands-on learning using OSS EDA tools can expand access to hardware design education and align with industrial needs. Embedding OSH concepts in vocational, academic, and cross-sector curricula would equip graduates with collaborative and technical skills while lowering dependence on proprietary ecosystems. Open tooling and cloud-based design environments could thus turn the skills crisis into a capacity-building opportunity—transforming Europe's human capital into a foundation for long-term autonomy and innovation.

5.2.5 Recommendations for public policy and recognition efforts

Based on the synthesised findings, we recommend public policy to prioritise investments, but also public recognition efforts such as the European Open Source Awards to highlight significant contributions made, into:

- Developing certification schemes and clarifying implementation-specific details that enable robust and modular OSH business models despite proprietary component requirements.
- Advancing knowledge and establishing practical business models that leverage OSH for sustainable revenue streams and clarifying the distinction between commodity and differentiating technologies.
- Fostering a culture and practice of sharing, collaboration, and knowledge diffusion in open hardware ecosystems to accelerate innovation cycles and market entry.
- Addressing the critical skills shortage in hardware and semiconductor design through education reform, OSS tooling, and scalable, hands-on learning initiatives that diversify and grow Europe's technical workforce.

5.3 The policy perspective

5.3.1 Increasing policy push for building European capabilities

The European Chips Act (Regulation 2023/1781) represent a major step in embedding open source as a central driver of innovation and technological sovereignty across the EU's industrial and digital policy landscape. The Chips Act introduced structural mechanisms—such as Integrated

Production Facilities and Open EU Foundries—to strengthen Europe’s semiconductor value chain through shared infrastructure and open design tooling.

These provisions emphasize that Europe’s technological sovereignty depends not solely on local production, but on collaboratively maintained open ecosystems that reduce dependency on closed, foreign-controlled technologies. In parallel, the Chips for Europe Initiative under Horizon Europe and the Digital Europe Programme supports projects combining semiconductor design, EDA tool development, and RISC-V-based architectures under open governance models, fostering both innovation reuse and industrial resilience.

In industry, OSH provides a strategic tool that can help to steer industries, grow ecosystems, and commoditise technologies. It can be a lever for laggards to catch-up with the leaders. Similar rationale extends to the geopolitical context. For Europe, OSS and OSH should be embraced for growing common platforms and infrastructure and used as a strategic mean to accelerate development for its industries.

5.3.2 Balancing sovereignty efforts on cutting-edge vs. legacy silicon technology

Europe’s reliance on non-EU foundries (TSMC, Samsung, GlobalFoundries) exposes vulnerabilities in its digital value chains. The European Chips Act (2023/1781) attempts to reduce these dependencies by boosting domestic manufacturing and R&D through the Chips for Europe Initiative and Open EU Foundries. However, building or scaling European fabrication capacity is hindered by high investment costs, foundry access constraints, and long qualification cycles. Interview findings emphasise that SME participation in chip design remains low due to the expense and time (1–2 years) required for access to non-European foundries.

While Intel’s new Magdeburg facility symbolises industrial progress, its US ownership underscores persistent sovereignty concerns. A business strategy focused on legacy and special-node production—where Europe leads industrial and automotive applications—appears more viable than chasing leading-edge competition. Firms such as X-Fab, Infineon, and STMicroelectronics exemplify the niche autonomy pathway combining open IP with reliable local manufacturing.

5.3.3 Value difficult to quantify, but rimes with open source software in qualitative terms

Quantifying the economic and societal value of OSH remains an unresolved challenge, largely because its benefits are diffuse, collaborative, and rooted in qualitative outcomes rather than direct revenue metrics. Unlike software, where distribution and use can be digitally tracked, OSH depends on physical fabrication and diverse application contexts, making data collection fragmented. However, the underlying value parallels OSS—interoperability, innovation reuse, and ecosystem resilience—while also adding unique tangible dimensions, such as local production potential, scientific reproducibility, and reduced dependency on single suppliers.

The available evidence suggests that OSH’s qualitative impact is most visible in its ability to democratize manufacturing, lower entry barriers for experimentation, and drive distributed problem-solving across industrial, academic, and citizen-engineering settings. Capturing this value

will require hybrid approaches that link social, scientific, and economic indicators, reflecting how openness amplifies autonomy and innovation far beyond conventional market measures.

5.3.4 Public funding for open source hardware

Public funding for open hardware is also evolving. Unlike the earlier years where funding was scarce and open access was rarely prioritised, there is growing recognition of hardware's strategic value, accompanied by more explicit calls for open sharing of research and results. Increasingly, public institutions are providing targeted support, recognising that hardware development often requires coordination among teams rather than isolated individual projects.

Examples in Europe, such as Germany's Sovereign Tech Fund, illustrate an emerging commitment to funding critical OSS infrastructure through public investment and policy changes. While challenges remain—especially in securing investment where traditional expectations around intellectual property and liability persist—the ecosystem is becoming more favourable for open hardware ventures, with a gradual rise in awareness about OSH and its benefits.

There is also a need for initiatives in Europe akin to the Next Generation Internet (NGI) program but focused on hardware. As commercial interest in OSH grows, new players are entering the field, though many are inexperienced in open models and may be hesitant due to perceived investment risks without conventional IP protections such as patents. Establishing a robust funding landscape, encouraging regulatory clarity, and building community knowledge will be critical for enabling commercial success and sustainable growth in the European OSH sector.

5.3.5 Recommendations for public policy and recognition efforts

Based on the synthesised findings, we recommend public policy to prioritise investments, but also public recognition efforts such as the European Open Source Awards to highlight significant contributions made, into:

- Advancing open collaboration and shared infrastructure under the European Chips Act to build European technological capabilities and strengthen industrial sovereignty through open ecosystems.
- Balancing Europe's semiconductor sovereignty efforts by developing sustainable capacity in legacy and special-node technologies while maintaining competitiveness in strategic sectors.
- Expanding equitable access to design and Electronic Design Automation (EDA) tools to lower entry barriers for SMEs, researchers, and educators across all types of OSH.
- Demonstrating and measuring the qualitative (or quantitative) value of OSH through its contributions to interoperability, local manufacturing, and open innovation.
- Establishing sustainable public funding mechanisms and investment frameworks that support OSH development, community building, and long-term ecosystem resilience in Europe.

5.4 The developer perspective

5.4.1 Mistakes expensive and harder to fix

A defining difference between OSS and OSH stems from the material nature of hardware development—mistakes cannot be easily undone. In OSS, errors can be corrected through version control, re-compilation, and automated testing pipelines; the cost of iteration is thus low, and feedback loops are fast. OSH, by contrast, bears immediate physical and financial consequences when a flaw emerges, as even a minor design error can render prototypes useless or require re-fabrication—each step involving material, labour, and often long lead-time expenses.

Beyond flaws and errors there is also legal risks that can have detrimental impacts for the OSH manufacturers. If a contribution is covered by a patent and ends up in silicon, it could cost the manufacturer “millions” as expressed by one interviewee. Even if the IP is released under a permissive license with a patent clause, it could have been contributed by a rogue employee, causing endless pain to all companies involved. Similarly, IP could incorporate unwanted code (e.g. security vulnerabilities) from malicious actors, also a risk needing careful consideration.

These risks amplifies the need for stronger validation, cautious experimentation, and higher up-front design precision. For community-led OSH projects, where resources are scarcer than in corporate R&D, such stakes often discourage openness during early stages and reinforce the pattern of “open when ready.” Yet, they also highlight the importance of robust simulation tools and shared prototyping facilities that could collectively lower the cost of learning and iteration.

5.4.2 High-quality electronic design and simulation (EDA and CAD/CAM/CAE) tools needed but often proprietary

Effective OSH development depends on advanced design and simulation environments that can minimise costly errors before physical production. For silicon chips, Electronic Design Automation (EDA) tools serve this need. However the most capable options for silicon chip design—offered by Synopsys, Cadence, and Siemens—remain proprietary and expensive, with two out of three geographically situated outside Europe. Their dominance limits education, experimentation, and digital sovereignty for European researchers and small firms alike. From the sovereignty perspective, interviewees still consider the position of Siemens as a strong sign for Europe.

Corresponding OSS tools such as Yosys, OpenROAD, Verilator, Magic, and Cocotb is reported to have matured and provide a comprehensive EDA toolchain but still lack the deep integration, advanced node support, and production verification capabilities that characterize the proprietary suites from Synopsys, Cadence, and Siemens. In practice, OSS EDA tools for silicon chip design is described as well-suited for academic research, FPGA workflows, and OSH design, while industrial-scale semiconductor projects continue to rely on the proprietary ecosystems for sign-off reliability and advanced-foundry compatibility.

For PCB design, the lag between proprietary options and the open alternatives such as KiCAD is much less, to large benefit to CERN and others who are actively using and contributing to the tools development. For mechanical design including CAD/CAM/CAE, FreeCAD provides basic

functionality with a rich ecosystem of add-on functionality but still lag behind proprietary CAD options.

Independent of area, interviewees agree on the imbalance of skills and general capabilities between Europe and the rest of the world. They also converge in the need to address this imbalance through strengthening of community-driven OSS design and simulation tools and integrating them into public research programs—such as through Chips JU and DE:Sign—are critical. This is described as not only technical priority, but also a question of strategic investment in autonomy and skill development.

5.4.3 Fabrication typically complex and costly

Physical production remains one of the largest barriers differentiating OSH from OSS. While software compiles at the speed of thought, hardware requires tooling, materials, and manufacturing partners—each adding cost, time, and administrative burden. Prototyping cycles can be prohibitively expensive, especially at the chip level where access to foundries demands both financial capital and compliance with technical and legal frameworks. As a result, even openly designed boards or circuits often depend on commercial fabrication services, limiting participation to those with institutional or industrial backing.

Community makerspaces and initiatives like OpenMPW and TinyTapeout have begun reducing this gap by offering shared multi-project fabrication runs, but the scale and inclusivity remain modest compared to the ubiquity of cloud-based deployment in OSS. Lowering these barriers—through subsidised foundry access, regional prototyping hubs, or shared fabrication credits under European programmes—would substantially widen the circle of open hardware contributors.

5.4.4 Verification and Quality Assurance critical for trust and reuse

Trust in OSH hinges on rigorous verification. Every design modification must be validated across configurations to guarantee performance, safety, and replicability—a process that can consume two-thirds of engineering time in commercial contexts. Unlike software, which benefits from incremental bug reporting and version-driven fixes, hardware requires holistic re-testing; a single altered line of Verilog may cascade into complete re-verification.

This complexity slows community contributions and explains why only a few projects, such as lowRISC, have achieved large-scale adoption of open intellectual-property (IP) blocks. Developing shared, automated test frameworks and standard verification libraries could distribute the workload across the OSH community—mirroring automated testing's transformative role in OSS and enabling trust-based collaboration at industrial scale.

5.4.5 Documentation critical but often missing with knowledge tacit

In OSH, inadequate documentation remains a chronic weakness. Whereas OSS embeds its rationale within readable code and traceable commits, hardware designs often obscure decisions about materials, geometries, or assembly processes. Essential contextual knowledge—the “why” behind design choices—frequently resides with individual creators rather than within accessible

archives. This tacit dependency impedes reuse, reproducibility, and onboarding of new contributors.

Improving documentation practices demands not just better templating of design files but cultural incentives that treat design rationale as integral to the artifact itself. Comprehensive bills of materials, annotated CAD models, and community-maintained wikis could transform how OSH knowledge circulates, allowing future iterators to inherit understanding rather than merely schematics.

5.4.6 Projects often open when ready rather than openly developed

Most hardware projects still follow a pattern of releasing designs only post-completion, driven by institutional norms, IP caution, and the fear of exposing immature work. This “open when ready” approach contrasts with the iterative transparency of software development where communities co-create in real time. Hidden development phases limit peer review, replication, and early community engagement—constraining the collective learning that has made OSS ecosystems thrive.

Interviewees emphasize that truly sustainable OSH requires a shift to openly developed workflows, where iteration, feedback, and accountability are shared from the outset. For Europe, fostering such openness could be encouraged through funding incentives, recognised metrics of collaborative process quality, and clearer legal templates for shared authorship and liability.

5.4.7 Tools and infrastructure missing collaborative workflows

Collaboration in open hardware is hindered by the absence of integrated, version-controlled environments comparable to GitHub or GitLab for software. Hardware design tools—particularly CAD and EDA suites—rarely support concurrent editing, difference tracking, or merge management, making distributed co-creation cumbersome. Projects like OpenFlexure demonstrate the potential of adopting code-centric or parametric design workflows, enabling contributions through familiar software platforms.

Yet, mainstream hardware development remains fragmented across proprietary tools and file formats. Bridging this gap calls for open, cloud-based collaboration ecosystems that interconnect design files, simulation data, and manufacturing instructions under transparent governance—an evolution that could eventually bring the same participatory scale to hardware that software enjoys today.

5.4.8 Recommendations for public policy and recognition efforts

Based on the synthesised findings, we recommend public policy to prioritise investments, but also public recognition efforts such as the European Open Source Awards to highlight significant contributions made, into:

- Reducing the risks and costs of hardware prototyping by promoting shared validation, simulation, and accessible prototyping infrastructures that make open hardware development more resilient.

- Expanding access to high-quality, open, and sovereign electronic design and simulation (EDA) tools that enable fair participation in advanced hardware innovation.
- Overcoming fabrication complexity and cost barriers by fostering shared foundry access, open manufacturing hubs, and community-enabled production initiatives.
- Establishing reliable verification and quality-assurance frameworks that enhance trust, reproducibility, and industry adoption of open hardware designs.
- Advancing transparent documentation standards and practices that capture not only design data but also knowledge and rationale to improve reuse and accessibility.
- Promoting openly developed hardware practices that invite collaboration throughout the design process, replacing “open when ready” with iterative openness and shared authorship.
- Building integrated, open collaboration infrastructures that connect design, simulation, and production workflows, fostering scalable community participation similar to OSS ecosystems.

5.5 The governance perspective

5.5.1 Hardware governance closed behind company doors

As OSH projects mature and interface with large-scale production and commercial markets, governance increasingly consolidates within single organisations or vendor-backed entities. This concentration—typified by companies such as Arduino and Lime behind products like LimeSDR—reflects both practical necessity and structural limitation. Hardware demands significant upfront investment, liability management, and coordinated manufacturing pipelines, which naturally push day-to-day decision-making toward firm-led hierarchies. Yet this model risks reproducing closed governance in ostensibly open ecosystems, where project direction, design priorities, and community engagement mechanisms remain largely internal. The openness is maintained at the level of access to design files, not participation in their creation, leaving users in a consumer role rather than as co-developers.

This “corporate-centric openness” provides brand reliability and product consistency but limits transparency, trust, and shared stewardship across the broader OSH community. Interviewees note that without collective decision-making structures—such as boards, advisory councils, or foundation-based frameworks—projects struggle to scale democratic governance while ensuring continuity and accountability. The trajectory mirrors earlier stages in OSS before the emergence of hybrid models integrating business sustainability with genuine community representation. For OSH, developing these plural governance mechanisms remains critical: not to dilute company leadership but to broaden ownership, legitimise public contribution, and ensure that open hardware ecosystems evolve as commons guided by many rather than guarded by a few.

5.5.2 Stewards opens up project governance and enable public-private partnerships

Neutral stewardship provides a means for opening up the governance, and creating a sustainable foundation for community growth and collaboration, including both public, private, and academic partners. Non-profit stewards—such as OpenFlexure project (backed by the Humanitarian

Technology Trust⁹¹), Open Source Imaging Initiative⁹², WhiteRabbit Collaboration⁹³ (hosted at CERN), and the OpenHW Foundation⁹⁴—act as neutral custodians, providing governance, legal stability, and policy engagement capabilities that grassroots or academic projects typically lack. Their role mirrors that of long-standing software foundations, ensuring openness remains compatible with commercial participation and regulatory frameworks. By offering formal legal identities, stewards enable OSH projects to engage in certification, procurement, and public funding while maintaining community integrity and distributed manufacturing potential—a challenging balance in the context of tangible products.

However, stewardship structures in OSH remain the exception rather than the rule, with most projects still dependent on university governance or informal leadership. The material and regulatory complexity of hardware has slowed the establishment of durable institutions comparable to those in OSS, such as the Linux Foundation or Eclipse Foundation. Interviewees underline that without capable stewards, OSH projects risk fragmentation or premature commercial capture, losing the collaborative ethos central to openness. Building more such neutral, well-resourced organisations in Europe is essential—both to safeguard the commons character of open hardware and to secure its place as a credible, policy-aligned pillar of digital sovereignty.

5.5.3 Institutional governance in R&D primed towards closed models and values

Institutional governance remains a central bottleneck for the mainstreaming of OSH in research and innovation. Most Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) still function under IP-centred models designed for proprietary licensing rather than collaborative design, making them ill-suited to steward open ecosystems. Their institutional logic prioritises control, profit, and exclusivity, creating friction for researchers who wish to release designs under open licences. While this structure once drove commercialisation efficiency, it now struggles to accommodate distributed modes of innovation that depend on shared ownership, rapid iteration, and community participation. Consequently, the potential of OSH as a research valorisation tool remains underexploited in academia and publicly funded projects.

In contrast, emerging OSPOs are beginning to shift the narrative—from openness as an exception to openness as institutional practice. By aligning TTOs, legal, and research departments under common principles, OSPOs promote licensing transparency, open workflows, and long-term collaboration⁹⁵. As exemplified by CERN⁹⁶ and Trinity College Dublin⁹⁷, more R&D as well as

⁹¹ <https://httrust.org/>

⁹² <https://www.opensourceimaging.org/>

⁹³ <https://www.white-rabbit.tech/>

⁹⁴ <https://openhwfoundation.org/>

⁹⁵ <https://www.linaker.se/blog/public-sector-open-source-program-offices/>

⁹⁶ <https://ospo.docs.cern.ch/>

Academic institutions should start establishing their own OSPOs, focusing on open science at large, encompassing both OSH and OSS, as well as other forms of open technology such as Open Data and Open Source AI.

5.5.4 Recommendations for public policy and recognition efforts

Based on the synthesised findings, we recommend public policy to prioritise investments, but also public recognition efforts such as the European Open Source Awards to highlight significant contributions made, into:

- Opening governance structures in commercial open hardware projects to make decision making and development more transparent, participatory, and community driven.
- Building and sustaining independent non-profit stewards that provide neutral governance, legal stability, and community support for open hardware ecosystems.
- Reforming institutional governance models to align TTOs and universities with the principles of open collaboration, shared ownership, and stewardship in OSH.
- Creation and standardisation of OSPOs across research-intensive organisations and wider scientific community to promote adoption and open science practices through OSH, OSS and other types of open technologies

⁹⁷ <https://www.tcd.ie/innovation/for-trinity-innovators/open-source-programme-office/>

6 Cross-case analysis on Open Source Software

Below, we provide a broader and overarching analysis of the challenges and opportunities across OSS from the different lenses of legal, business, policy, development, and governance. We accordingly propose specific aspects and types of contributions that are of specific importance to invest in, as well as recognise and promote to help foster OSS adoption in the EU, and by extension helping to advance its sovereignty and competitiveness in the global setting.

6.1 Legal Perspective

6.1.1 Compliance and administrative burden due to increased regulation

The emergence of new European frameworks—most notably the AI Act, the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA), and the proposed Cloud and AI Development Act—has expanded the legal obligations placed on OSS developers. Compliance now includes requirements for traceability, cybersecurity measures, and risk-based classifications, even for non-commercial or community-led projects. While these measures aim to improve transparency and accountability, they risk disproportionately burdening small developers and volunteer maintainers who lack legal or administrative resources. Larger enterprises and consortia such as Gaia-X, 8ra, and Linux Foundation Europe have greater capacity to institutionalize compliance, widening disparities within the OSS ecosystem. This asymmetry creates barriers to entry and slows innovation in precisely the areas the EU seeks to strengthen.

6.1.2 Balancing between open licensing and standard essential patents

The energy and telecommunications sectors demonstrate the legal dimensions of standardization and licensing. Grid operators and network providers navigate overlapping regulatory regimes tied to safety, interoperability, and intellectual property rights. Here, OSS functions as both a compliance mechanism and a subject of legal contention. The movement toward open standardisation—exemplified by LF Energy in the power sector and OpenAirInterface in telecom—repositions licensing from a proprietary control instrument to a governance tool consistent with EU competition and procurement law. However, reconciliation between OSS licenses and the preservation of standard-essential patents remains complex, particularly in industries with long product lifecycles and established patent portfolios.

6.1.3 Regulatory conservatism inhibiting open source adoption

In healthcare, legal constraints appear most restrictive. Regulatory conservatism—driven by patient safety obligations, privacy norms under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and public procurement rules—limits experimentation with OSS systems despite their alignment with transparency and interoperability goals. Compliance costs, coupled with liability uncertainties, discourage adoption among resource-constrained institutions.

6.1.4 Structural Imbalances in Legal Governance and Enforcement

A general pattern across all sectors is the dominance of well-established industrial and governmental actors in shaping legal compliance practices. Large corporations and consortia have the structural advantage to engage directly in EU standard-setting and regulatory consultations, whereas community projects remain underrepresented in policymaking. This centralization of governance leads to an imbalance: regulations intended to secure open collaboration often strengthen hierarchical control and compliance gatekeeping.

6.1.5 Recommendations for public policy and recognition efforts

Based on the synthesised findings, we recommend public policy to prioritise investments, but also public recognition efforts such as the European Open Source Awards to highlight significant contributions made, into:

- The compliance and administrative burdens facing OSS developers under emerging EU regulations such as the AI Act and Cyber Resilience Act.
- The legal and technical conflicts between OSS licensing and standard-essential patents, particularly in industrial and telecommunications contexts.
- The liability and accountability uncertainties hindering OSS adoption in highly regulated sectors like healthcare and mobility.
- The asymmetries in representation and influence between community-driven projects and large industrial actors in shaping OSS governance and regulatory policy.
- The lack of sustained funding and stewardship mechanisms for maintaining compliance, security, and longevity of critical OSS components in Europe.

6.2 Policy Perspective

6.2.1 Strategic investments vital but unbalanced

Strategic investment emerges as a unifying policy instrument. In artificial intelligence, cloud, and edge computing, the EU has launched programs such as the AI Factories network, IPCEI-CIS, and the Cloud and AI Development Act, all designed to stimulate OSS innovation and ensure that critical infrastructure remains subject to European governance. Public investment is strategically deployed not simply to generate new technologies, but to foster ecosystem resilience and independence from global hyperscalers. Still, funding for OSS efforts remains fragmented and inconsistent where domains such as healthcare, agriculture, and manufacturing suffer from sporadic support, inhibiting the development and sustainability of OSS projects. Smaller initiatives or SME-led projects frequently lack long-term funding, elevating the risk of abandonment after initial pilot phases.

6.2.2 Ecosystem collaboration necessary but restrained in R&D

Ecosystem development is explicitly fostered through the creation of collaborative frameworks (e.g., 8ra, NeoNephos, LF Energy), with policies aiming to bridge the gap between industrial actors, research institutions, and public stakeholders. Still, policy efforts to encourage collaborative ecosystems are often stymied by siloed sectoral interests and weak industry-linkages. The report highlights discord between research-driven OSS output and operational industrial uptake—most visible in energy and healthcare, where Horizon-funded projects frequently end without industrialization. The lack of clear policy guidance for open data, code reuse, and post-grant maintenance exacerbates fragmentation and reduces the practical impact of public investment in OSS.

6.2.3 Procurement used as policy instrument but limited by conservative practice

In energy and mobility, policy incentives have catalysed large-scale collaboration and sector-wide standards by integrating OSS development into public procurement and modernization programs. However, conservative procurement practices—especially in healthcare, mobility, and public administration—create significant obstacles for OSS adoption, favouring incumbent vendors and proprietary solutions. Open-by-default policies articulated at the national or EU level often fail to translate into operational procurement criteria, leading to closed technology stacks and siloed system deployments. Public sector institutions cite liability, maintenance, and integration risks as justifications for continued reliance on established vendors, even where open alternatives exist.

6.2.4 Skills Shortages and Capacity Constraints

Skills, talent, and capacity building are recurring policy challenges and focus areas, particularly in mature sectors such as telecom and manufacturing. Programs to strengthen the AI talent pipeline (e.g., the AI Skills Academy) and incentives for up-skilling in automotive OSS initiatives are explicitly referenced. Where such policies are absent or poorly aligned with sectoral demands, adoption lags and ecosystem fragmentation persists.

6.2.5 Strategic Autonomy and Sustainability Tensions

EU policy strongly emphasizes digital sovereignty and reduction of dependency on non-European providers, but strategic autonomy efforts can inadvertently fragment the ecosystem or create parallel infrastructures rather than fostering shared platforms. Balancing open collaboration with autonomy goals requires nuanced policy design—overly restrictive requirements risk stifling innovation, while uncoordinated national initiatives may duplicate effort and undermine the potential for Europe-wide standards.

6.2.6 Recommendations for public policy and recognition efforts

Based on the synthesised findings, we recommend public policy to prioritise investments, but also public recognition efforts such as the European Open Source Awards to highlight significant contributions made, into:

- Bridging fragmented and inconsistent public investment to create sustainable OSS projects and platforms.
- Overcoming conservative procurement policies and vendor lock-in to enable broader adoption of OSS solutions in the public and private sectors.
- Building collaborative ecosystems and effective industry-academia linkages that transfer OSS innovation into operational practice.
- Addressing digital skills shortages and capacity gaps to empower more organizations and individuals to contribute to and benefit from OSS development.
- Advancing strategic autonomy for Europe while promoting coordination and shared digital infrastructure rather than duplication or fragmentation.

6.3 Business Perspective

6.3.1 Both opportunities and barriers for Open Source solution providers

From a business perspective, OSS is widely recognized as a means to accelerate digital transformation, reduce development costs, and mitigate vendor lock-in. In sectors such as artificial intelligence (AI), cloud-edge computing, and telecommunications, enterprise surveys suggest widespread integration of OSS components—over 50% of AI/ML projects in surveyed organizations use OSS software, for instance, with highest adoption in education, manufacturing, retail, and finance. In these sectors, open standards and OSS technologies are credited with enabling market entry for SMEs, supporting interoperability, and fostering collaborative innovation models that enhance competitiveness and resilience.

Still, many organizations encounter difficulties in entering markets dominated by incumbent vendors and proprietary solutions, particularly in sectors like healthcare, telecom, and public administration. Conservative procurement policies and pre-existing vendor relationships often lead to vendor lock-in, making it hard for OSS solutions or new entrants to compete, regardless of their technical merit.

6.3.2 Resource Limitations in Skills, Talent, and Capacity

The shortage of skilled contributors and internal capacity within the European industrial ecosystem limits the development and integration of OSS solutions, especially in manufacturing, agriculture, and telecom. Skills gaps manifest in areas like DevOps, cloud orchestration, AI/ML, and security expertise, slowing innovation and diminishing ROI from OSS engagement. Larger firms and consortia have more resources to upskill staff, while SMEs and startups often struggle to keep pace.

6.3.3 Foundations and consortia critical for enabling ecosystem collaboration

Foundations and consortia—such as the Linux Foundation Energy, and sector-specific groups like Open Logistics Foundation—play a central role in facilitating sustainability, funding, and ecosystem development, providing neutral forums for public and private actors. Public funding, incentives, and regulatory encouragement align business interests toward the development of federated

platforms and common standards. In areas where strong foundation and consortia structures are missing, business use of open source is often hindered by fragmented collaboration between industry, research, and community actors, with projects failing to scale or be adopted after initial pilots. This is evident in sectors like agriculture and manufacturing, where many promising OSS projects remain isolated or underutilized.

6.3.4 Business Model and Sustainability Constraints

Businesses that actively participate in OSS report improvements in time-to-market, cost predictability, and adaptability to evolving standards. However, competition over differentiation and the ability to capture market value from shared technology platforms present ongoing challenges. The sustainability of projects, especially those critical to industrial processes, depends on continued investment from both public and private sources, as well as mechanisms for governance and compliance that are responsive to business realities.

6.3.5 Cultural Resistance and Standardization Barriers

Organisational inertia, preference for proprietary approaches, and scepticism regarding open standards and OSS can delay or limit business adoption, even in sectors that stand to benefit. In telecom and manufacturing, transitioning from proprietary to OSS frameworks requires changes in culture, product lifecycles, and approaches to standardization. These shifts often move more slowly in industries with long-established structures or safety-critical requirements.

6.3.6 Recommendations for public policy and recognition efforts

Based on the synthesised findings, we recommend public policy to prioritise investments, but also public recognition efforts such as the European Open Source Awards to highlight significant contributions made, into:

- Lowering market entry barriers and reducing vendor lock-in to open new opportunities for OSS businesses and SMEs.
- Developing sustainable business models and stewardship strategies to ensure the long-term viability and maintenance of OSS projects.
- Addressing skill shortages and building capacity among contributors, companies, and European industries to accelerate OSS development and adoption.
- Strengthening collaboration within fragmented ecosystems by connecting industry, research, and community stakeholders for collective impact.
- Navigating regulatory complexity, commercial liability, and compliance issues to support secure and responsible OSS business practices.
- Overcoming organizational inertia and cultural resistance to foster the adoption of open standards and collaborative innovation models.

6.4 Developer Perspective

6.4.1 Opportunities of open source requires dedicated resources and capabilities

OSS offers developers the chance to engage in collaborative problem-solving, rapid prototyping, and skills development. Participation in OSS projects exposes developers to peer review, distributed teamwork, and diverse technical challenges, which are especially valuable in sectors characterized by rapid change, such as artificial intelligence, cloud computing, and telecommunications. However, disparities in resources, recognition, and institutional support are evident. In fields such as manufacturing, healthcare, and agriculture, developers report difficulty finding organizational resources for long-term maintenance, while public funding often favours short-term innovation over ongoing stewardship.

6.4.2 Increasing regulation adds additional technical requirements to maintainers

Regulatory changes, such as the AI Act, introduce new documentation, risk management, and traceability requirements. While these may increase confidence in OSS components, they also add compliance burdens that are easier for large organizations to bear than for individual maintainers or small teams. Maintaining the security of OSS projects is already a pervasive challenge, especially as visibility increases the risk of vulnerability exposure, malicious contribution, and adversarial attack. This is particularly urgent in sectors like AI, cloud, and cybersecurity, where robust review processes, regular audits, and adoption of best practices from bodies such as the OpenSSF are essential but often under-resourced.

6.4.3 Sustainability and long-term maintenance at risk

Sustaining high code quality and maintainability over time requires long-term commitment and resources. Many projects—especially those originating from academia or grant funding—risk abandonment once initial support runs out. Technical debt, lack of continuous integration/testing infrastructure, and the uneven availability of skilled maintainers compromise the longevity and reliability of critical OSS components, as seen in flagship AI libraries and energy grid tools. If the increased burden and requirements added by new regulations is not managed, the sustainability of many projects will be threatened even further.

6.4.4 Support at scale with onboarding and human infrastructure needed

The European experience highlights the importance of collaborative communities and neutral platforms in enabling cross-border project continuity and helping developers keep pace with evolving technical and regulatory standards. Developer skill-building, code review, and upskilling programs are particularly emphasized in sectors undergoing rapid digital transformation, such as automotive and telecom, where OSS adoption requires new expertise in DevOps, cloud, and network orchestration. Foundations and consortia providing stewardship and pooling of resources fills an important void by helping to address such challenges. This report specifically highlights how comprehensive documentation and robust testing practices are often lacking, especially in projects primarily driven by volunteers or academia. Insufficient onboarding materials and limited

access to automated testing environments slow adoption and hinder new contributors, with the effect most pronounced in complex domains like cloud orchestration, scientific computing, and telecom network management.

6.4.5 Recommendations for public policy and recognition efforts

Based on the synthesised findings, we recommend public policy to prioritise investments, but also public recognition efforts such as the European Open Source Awards to highlight significant contributions made, into:

- Ensuring robust security and effective vulnerability management in OSS projects, especially for critical infrastructure and software components.
- Sustaining high levels of code quality, maintainability, and long-term support for OSS technologies.
- Achieving interoperability, integration, and scalability of OSS solutions across complex and legacy industry environments.
- Providing comprehensive documentation, automated testing, and superior developer experience to facilitate the adoption and contribution to OSS projects.
- Translating research-driven OSS development into widely adopted, production-ready tools in operational and industrial contexts.
- Addressing technical skill gaps and fostering collaborative development practices across sectors and communities.

6.5 Governance Perspective

6.5.1 Shift from hierarchical to multistakeholder, ecosystem-based models

From a governance perspective, the development and adoption of OSS software across European sectors (like the Automotive industry) exemplify a shift from hierarchical, vendor-driven control toward multistakeholder, ecosystem-based models of coordination and stewardship. Governance of OSS involves how technical directions, resource allocations, inclusion of contributors, and long-term sustainability are determined processes that now span governments, industry consortia, foundations, academia, and the OSS community itself.

6.5.2 Role of Neutral Orchestrating Entities

Major pan-European initiatives such as 8ra, NeoNephos, Gaia-X, and sectoral efforts like LF Energy and the Open Logistics Foundation serve as neutral orchestrating entities. They facilitate collaboration across industry, research, and public administration while ensuring that governance frameworks foster both innovation and alignment with European policy goals. These governance models often feature multi-party steering committees, open technical working groups, and membership or sponsorship tiers that blend public and private interests. In the energy sector, for example, grid operators and domain-specialist enterprises like Alliander and RTE use LF Energy as a neutral platform to co-develop solutions, sharing not only code but also strategic planning and operational risk.

6.5.3 Neutral Platforms as Stewards of Digital Infrastructure

These neutral platforms act as stewards of shared digital infrastructure and enable the pooling of resources necessary for project maintenance, compliance, security, and documentation. The presence of such neutral governance bodies aligns with the EU's ambition to embed principles of transparency, inclusivity, and digital sovereignty in mission-critical software developed and deployed across the region.

6.5.4 Persistent Tensions in Governance Practice

Despite these advances, challenges persist in balancing openness and control. Issues arise around licensing and IP, navigating competition between industry partners, assuring the sustainability of community-driven projects, and ensuring consistent participation from all relevant stakeholders. In regulated sectors such as healthcare and telecom, traditional procurement and compliance requirements can stifle collaborative governance models or limit their impact to less critical system layers.

6.5.5 Transition Toward Collaborative and Modular Governance

The overall trend indicates a move from siloed, closed, and proprietary management toward open, modular, and collaborative forms. This evolution is supported by both EU policy (e.g., open-by-default principles, support for open standards) and practical necessity, as digital transformation and cross-border interoperability become central to sectoral modernisation. However, governance effectiveness is contingent on ongoing institutional support, cross-sector skill building, and the cultivation of trust among actors with divergent interests.

6.5.6 Recommendations for public policy and recognition efforts

Based on the synthesised findings, we recommend public policy to prioritise investments, but also public recognition efforts such as the European Open Source Awards to highlight significant contributions made, into:

- Building inclusive, transparent, and neutral governance structures that balance the interests of public, private, and community stakeholders.
- Sustaining long-term stewardship and funding mechanisms to maintain critical OSS infrastructure and shared digital assets.
- Ensuring balanced representation and equitable decision-making across small contributors, large enterprises, and public institutions.
- Bridging gaps between research, community projects, and industrial deployment through coordinated governance frameworks.
- Managing intellectual property, licensing, and standards in ways that promote openness, interoperability, and fair competition.
- Strengthening institutional trust, accountability, and collaboration across cross-sector ecosystems to support digital sovereignty.

7 Conclusions

This report highlights how Open Source Software (OSS) and Open Source Hardware (OSH) have become foundational enablers of Europe's competitiveness, technological autonomy, and digital sovereignty. Together, they represent not only tools for innovation but also models of governance and collaboration that align with the values of openness, transparency, and shared stewardship central to the European digital agenda. Across both software and hardware domains, the findings reveal an ecosystem in transition—from isolated, project-based efforts toward more structured, institutionalised, and policy-supported frameworks capable of sustaining long-term impact. The European Chips Act, the AI Continent Action Plan, the Interoperable Europe Act as well as initiatives such as IPCEI-CIS and the Chips Joint Undertaking signal a decisive policy push to embed open collaboration within industrial and technological strategy. Yet, realising this vision will require addressing persistent structural challenges.

In hardware, the challenges differ from software in key ways: mistakes are costlier, collaboration more complex, access to skilled workforce more limited, and entry barriers higher. The success of OSH depends on improving access to OSS Electronic Design Automation (EDA) tools, continued investments into open standards as RISC-V, creating collaboration-native tools and infrastructure, lowering fabrication costs, and supporting community-based verification and quality assurance models. The report identifies promising examples—OpenFlexure, Open Source Imaging Initiative, lowRISC, and the OpenHW Foundation—illustrating that durable stewardship structures, rather than isolated innovation, are essential for scaling and sustaining openness. However, the governance of many OSH initiatives remains closed. The entry-barriers provides some of the rationale for OSH projects (typically in open source silicon) being centred to business and academic circuits. Still, establishing neutral, non-profit stewards, public-private partnerships, and open institutional frameworks is key to ensuring that open ecosystems remain both democratic and economically viable, promoting knowledge-sharing and skills development, and thereby strengthening the autonomy and capabilities of Europe. Improving technology transfer, investing into academic programs, and increasing funding to R&D projects based on open standards and technology are also seen as critical, as most innovation in Europe originates from a small set of research groups across the continent.

For software, OSS has become a de facto way of building modern digital infrastructure through sharing and reuse. For Europe, OSS is in this way increasingly strategic rather than peripheral. In AI, cloud, and cybersecurity, openness is framed in regulatory and sovereignty terms—viewed as a means to secure trust, transparency, and resilience against external dependencies. In sectors such as energy, telecommunications, and automotive, OSS drives interoperability and shared innovation, with projects under foundations like LF Energy and the Eclipse SDV Working Group bridging industry-scale collaboration with public value. The challenge lies in turning these pockets of excellence into systemic practice—supported by sustainable funding for long-term maintenance, measurable recognition of contributions put in, and coordinated policy instruments

across ministries, research frameworks, and industry alliances to grow the capabilities necessary to leverage the full potential open technologies can bring.

Public recognition initiatives such as OS Awards.eu therefore play an important role not only in rewarding technical achievement but also in shaping the emerging culture of openness in Europe. Recognition can catalyse visibility, legitimacy, and accountability for individuals, organisations, and stewards who demonstrate the societal and industrial benefits of open collaboration. Building on the report's findings, recognition frameworks should celebrate those advancing shared governance, transparent tooling, reproducible science, or open industrial design—making openness itself a recognised dimension of European excellence. In doing so, Europe can anchor openness not merely as a compliance principle, but as a strategic and cultural asset for innovation, resilience, and societal progress.

8 Annex A – Survey questionnaire

We are thrilled to invite you to contribute your valuable expertise to OS Awards.EU, an EU-funded initiative dedicated to advancing Open Source Software (OSS) and Hardware (OSH) across Europe. Our mission is to raise public awareness, foster skills development, and highlight the transformative potential of OSS/OSH in enhancing Europe's competitiveness and digital sovereignty.

Open Source technologies play a crucial role in shaping the future of innovation, from powering critical infrastructure to enabling cutting-edge advancements in areas like artificial intelligence, cloud computing, and cybersecurity. They are also instrumental in driving transparency, collaboration, and sustainability in public services and industries alike.

Your insights will help us identify priority areas, critical stakeholders, and necessary skills to guide the future development of OSS/OSH. The results of this questionnaire will directly influence our roadmap for raising awareness and recognition of Open Source contributions in Europe.

The survey will take approximately 5–7 minutes to complete. We value your time and thank you for sharing your perspectives to help shape the future of Open Source innovation!

1. Demographic Information (Optional)

- What is your professional background?
- Developer/Engineer
- Researcher/Academic
- Policy Maker
- Industry Professional
- Other: [Text Box]

Which area of the open technology field do you primarily focus on?

(Select the option that best aligns with your work)

- Open Source Software Development
- Open Source Hardware Design
- Open Standards and Protocols
- Community Building and Advocacy
- Open Data and Open Knowledge
- Research and Academia related to Open Technologies
- Policy and Regulation for Open Source Adoption
- Enterprise/Industry Implementation of Open Solutions

- Other: [Text Box]

2. Technological Perspective

Which areas of technology will most benefit from OSS/OSH in the next 5 years?

(Select up to 3)

- Cloud Computing
- Cybersecurity
- Artificial Intelligence (AI)
- Internet of Things (IoT)
- Blockchain
- Edge Computing
- Other: [Text Box]
- Can you name one OSS/OSH project critical in these areas?

(Optional open-ended)

- What skills are most critical to sustaining OSS/OSH in these areas?

(Select up to 2)

- Advanced Programming
- Cybersecurity
- Community Building
- Leadership & Project Management
- Legal/Policy Expertise
- Other: [Text Box]

3. Societal Perspective

- Which public services or infrastructures rely most on OSS/OSH for their effectiveness?

(Select up to 3)

- Healthcare
- Education
- Public Administration
- Smart Cities

- Transportation
- Energy/Utilities
- Other: [Text Box]
- What is one OSS/OSH initiative or project you see as impactful in public services?

(Optional open-ended)

- Who are the key stakeholders in supporting OSS/OSH in public services?

(Select all that apply)

- Non-Governmental organisations (NGOs)
- Academic Institutions
- Public Sector
- Open Source Communities
- Large Enterprises
- Other: [Text Box]

4. Industrial Perspective

Which industries will see the greatest impact from OSS/OSH in the next 5 years?

(Select up to 3)

- Manufacturing
- Healthcare
- Telecommunications
- Energy
- Automotive
- Agriculture
- Other: [Text Box]
- Within those industries, what is one critical area where OSS/OSH can provide value?

(Optional open-ended)

Can you name one OSS/OSH project that is transforming or could transform these industries?

(Optional open-ended)

5. Closing and Follow-Up

Would you like to receive updates or participate further in the OS Awards.EU initiative?

- Yes
- No
- Any additional comments or ideas you would like to share?

(Optional open-ended)

9 Annex B – Interviewees

Table 3: List of interviewees surveyed in the second step of the research process underpinning this report.

Name	Role	Context
Jimmy Ahlberg	Director Open Source Policy at Ericsson	OSS
Jonne Soininen	Head of Open Source and Technology Vision at Nokia	OSS
Lucian Balea	Deputy Director of R&D and Open Source Director at RTE Réseau de Transport d'Electricité	OSS
Jonas van den Bogaard	Open Source Office Lead at Alliander	OSS
Luis Falcon	Project lead at GNU Health	OSS
Andrew Harding	Head of Tech Strategy at National Health Services (NHS)	OSS
Olle Johansson	Security consultant at Edvina	OSS
Claus Popp Larsen	Senior researcher at RISE	OSS
Chandra Challagonda	CEO at FIWARE	OSS
Robert Ahmann	Open Source specialist Bosch	OSS
Sumer Johal	Executive director at AgStack	OSS
Christopher Brewster	Professor at Maastricht University	OSS
Max Mehl	Open Source & Software Supply Chain at Deutsche Bahn	OSS
Anders Hammar	Developer at Samtrafiken	OSS
Brian Keegan	Associate professor at University of Boulder	OSS
Cosmin Oprea	Principal consultant at Synchron	OSS
Gabriele Columbro	Executive director at FINOS	OSS
Cailean Osborne	Senior Researcher at Linux Foundation	OSS
Joakim Eriksson	Senior Researcher at RISE	OSS
Alberto Marti	VP Open Innovation at OpenNebula	OSS
Daniel Melin	Business Developer at Safespring	OSS
Andrew Katz	CEO at Orcro Limited	OSH
Javier Serrano	Deputy Group Leader, Accelerator Controls, Electronics and Mechatronics at European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN)	OSH

David Cuartielles	Co-founder at Arduino	OSH
Allison Randal	Senior Researcher at Capabilities Limited	OSH
Cagatay Yilmaz	Project Manager at RISE	OSH
Olof Kindgren	Senior Digital Design Engineer at Qamcom, Co-founder and Director at FOSSi Foundation	OSH
Nadya Peek	Assistant Professor at University of Washington	OSH
Luca Benini	Professor at ETH Zurich	OSH
Martin Häuer	Board Member at Open Source Imaging Initiative e.V. (non-profit)	OSH
Javier Orensanz Martinez	CEO at lowRISC	OSH
Jenny Molloy	Assistant Research Professor at University of Cambridge	OSH
Michael Weinberg	Executive Director at NYU Law - Engelberg Center on Innovation Law and Policy	OSH
Mike Eftimakis	Founding Director at CHERI Alliance	OSH
Jaime Arredondo	Creator at Bold and Open	OSH
Krste Asanović	Professor at UC Berkeley, Chief Architect at SiFive	OSH
Pieter Hijma	Developer (Self-employed)	OSH
Richard Bowman	Founder of OpenFlexure project	OSH